

SPECTRUM

D6.1 Technical Blueprint for Compute and Data Continuum

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Abstract**Key Words**

High Performance Computing, HPC, High Energy Physics, HEP, Radio Astronomy, RA, compute and data continuum, storage, network, European Union, EU, supercomputing, AI, ML, quantum computing

This document presents a Technical Blueprint for a compute-and-data trans-continuum infrastructure design and architecture optimised for cost, power efficiency, time to results, and science-driven capability.

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Lead Partner	CERN		
Author(s)	<p>Lead Editors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eric Wulff (CERN) • Jeff Wagg (CNRS) • Maria Girone (CERN) <p>Contributors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Andrea Manzi (EGI Foundation) • Sergio Andreozzi (EGI Foundation) • Hans-Christian Hoppe (FZJ) • Luis Cifuentes (FZJ) • Shan Mignot (CNRS) • David Southwick (CERN) 		
Reviewers	Tommaso Boccali (INFN) John Swinbank (NWO-I ASTRON) Raymond Oonk (SURF)		
Moderated by	Patricia Ruiz		
Approved by	AMB		

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Terminology / Acronyms	
Terminology / Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CoP	Community of Practice
DocDB	EGI Document Database
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FLOPS	FLoating-point Operations Per Second
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
FTS	File Transfer Service
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHG	GreenHouse Gas
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HEP	High Energy Physics
HL-LHC	High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider
HTC	High-Throughput Computing
HPC	High Performance Computing
I/O	Input/Output
IT	Information Technology
JU	Joint Undertaking
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life-Cycle Assessment
LOFAR	LOw Frequency ARray
ML	Machine Learning
QCD	Quantum Chromodynamics
RA	Radio Astronomy
RI	Research Infrastructure
SKA	Square Kilometre Array
SKAO	SKA Observatory

SRCNet	SKA Regional Centre Network
SRIDA	Strategic Research, Innovation and Deployment Agenda
SSO	Single Sign On
WG	Working Group
Worldwide LHC Computing Grid	WLCG
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

European research communities are preparing for decades of data growth and increasing computational complexity. Infrastructures such as the High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) in High-Energy Physics (HEP), and Square Kilometre Array (SKA) and Low Frequency Array (LOFAR) in Radio Astronomy (RA) will generate unprecedented data volumes, and rely on highly sophisticated workflows for simulation, analysis, and real-time processing. Meeting these demands requires more than incremental improvements to existing infrastructures. It calls for a coherent compute and data continuum that links together high-performance computing, cloud platforms, edge devices, and large-scale data services in a way that is reliable and easy to use for the scientific communities.

This Technical Blueprint draws on the needs of the HEP and RA communities, but is designed to be more widely applicable to a large number of data intensive sciences, with similar computational needs. At its core, the continuum is defined by a set of interdependent capabilities, outlined in the blueprint capability map.

The analysis underpinning this blueprint shows that while many components already exist, significant gaps remain. Interfaces between infrastructures are often inconsistent, making interoperability a persistent challenge. Co-design between scientific communities and infrastructure providers is not systematic, which risks creating mismatches between what is built and what is needed. Portability of software across diverse architectures is still limited, particularly as accelerators become more common. Workflow management tools are not yet capable of seamless execution across multiple sites, and provenance capture is inconsistently applied. Provenance capture refers to the systematic recording of all information needed to understand, reproduce, and validate how a piece of data or a scientific result was produced. Trust and security mechanisms remain fragmented, slowing down cross-border and cross-domain collaboration. Finally, long-term sustainability, covering management of environmental impacts over the full lifecycle of the infrastructure, operational funding, and workforce development, remains a key concern for communities whose experiments will span decades.

This blueprint recommends a coordinated European effort to address these issues. Interfaces and standards must be harmonised to allow resources to interoperate smoothly. Co-design processes are to be strengthened so that major scientific projects can influence infrastructure roadmaps. Software portability and execution environments need investment to ensure that applications can exploit emerging hardware efficiently. Workflow orchestration must evolve into a cross-facility capability with built-in resilience and provenance. A federated trust and security framework is to be adopted, building on existing identity federations but extending them to new services and disciplines. AI/ML must be integrated as a core capability. Finally, policies regarding the use and the long-term management of the software and hardware resources are essential for sustainability. Together, these elements define a federated, sovereign, and future-proof infrastructure that will empower not only HEP and RA, but also other data-intensive domains to fully exploit Europe's scientific potential.

The Blueprint sets out how Europe can move from today's fragmented landscape toward an integrated, long-term continuum. By clearly defining which capabilities are needed, and identifying the most pressing gaps, it outlines a practical path for connecting compute, data, software, and security into a coherent infrastructure that is able to address the challenges for future data-intensive research. The approach is designed to be both technically realistic and aligned with the operational requirements of HEP, RA, and other scientific domains that depend on reliable, large-scale digital infrastructures, with strong focus on environmental sustainability and energy awareness.

By addressing these priorities, the Blueprint directly supports European policy goals of FAIR and open data, digital sovereignty, sustainability, and strategic autonomy. It provides a practical pathway to infrastructures that not only serve flagship communities such as HEP and RA but also strengthen Europe's position in the global landscape of data-intensive science.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The European scientific computing landscape is undergoing a major transition as communities prepare for the exascale era. High-Energy Physics (HEP) and Radio Astronomy (RA) are among the most demanding fields in terms of data and computation, and they illustrate the scale of the challenge ahead. These domains were selected as clear examples of future needs, with all the considerations being extendable to virtually all data-intensive scientific domains. The High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC), expected to start operations in 2029, will generate unprecedented data volumes. The two largest experiments, or particle detectors, at the LHC, namely ATLAS and CMS, are forecasting requirements for disk storage of approximately 3 EB and 1.5 EB respectively, while both forecast tape archival storage requirements of approximately 4–6 EB by the mid 2030s¹². At the same time, the Square Kilometre Array Observatory (SKAO) will produce continuous data streams requiring near real-time processing at data centers in the host countries, and then distribute up to 700 PB/year of scientific data for subsequent analysis to a network of regional centers referred to as the SKA Regional Centre Network (SRCNet).

High-performance computing (HPC) is set to become a core component for HEP and RA. HEP experiments have been using HPC resources for more than 15 years, with HPC now making significant contributions to both production and analysis pipelines^{3,4,5,6,7}. For example, the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG) already comprises approximately 1.4 million cores and over 1.5 EB of storage across 170 sites (home.cern), and HPC resources exploited by experiments range from 3 sites integrated by ALICE and LHCb, to more than 10 sites by ATLAS and CMS. The upcoming High-Luminosity LHC and SKAO will only increase these demands.

The European e-infrastructure ecosystem has grown organically over several decades and today includes national, international, and domain-specific initiatives. The [EuroHPC Joint Undertaking \(JU\)](#) provides access to leadership-class supercomputing resources through a network of petascale and exascale systems. The European Open Science Cloud ([EOSC](#)) serves as a federated environment for data, services, and software, enabling cross-disciplinary collaboration and FAIR data access across European research communities. The European Grid Infrastructure ([EGI](#)) Federation coordinates high-throughput computing resources across multiple member countries and domains. Domain-specific initiatives such as the WLCG and the emerging SRCNet address the particular needs of their scientific communities through specialized architectures and governance structures.

While these individual initiatives have achieved considerable success within their respective domains, the increasing convergence of scientific requirements, as outlined in Section 2 of this document, and the scale of emerging challenges necessitate a more integrated approach. By having a coherent, well integrated and accessible scalable compute and data continuum, the science community would benefit from economies of scale, increased efficiency, and the lowering of thresholds in difficulty for using the large-scale computing

¹CMS Phase-2 Computing Model: Update Document, CMS Offline Software and Computing (2022) <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2815292>

²ATLAS Software and Computing HL-LHC Roadmap, The ATLAS Collaboration (2022) <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2802918>

³Strategy for HPC Integration in WLCG/HEP, Maria Girone et al. (2025) <https://zenodo.org/records/15032799>

⁴US ATLAS and US CMS HPC and Cloud Blueprint, Fernando Barreiro Megino et al. (2023) <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.07376>

⁵Integrating the Perlmutter HPC system in the ALICE Grid, Sergiu Weisz et al. (2025) <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202533701107>

⁶Integrating LHCb workflows on HPC resources: status and strategies, Federico Stagni et al. (2020) <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202024509002>

⁷ Bard, D., Benjamin, D., Calafiura, P., Childers, T., Fisk, I., Girone, M., Gutsche, O., Hufnagel, D., Klimentov, A., Lancon, E., Martinez Outschoorn, V. I., & Wuerthwein, F. (2025). Strategy For HPC Integration (US) Whitepaper. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17854525>

resources available in Europe. These challenges are not only about raw computing power. They also raise questions about how infrastructures should be designed and operated in a world of growing data volumes and increasingly complex workflows. The grid infrastructures that have supported today's experiments have been remarkably successful, but they will need to evolve. In particular, it is important to distinguish between loosely coupled federation models, centred on federated identity, access control, and data-lake technologies, and strongly coupled federation models, which operate at the application layer and provide uniform job execution across sites. The former has seen broad uptake and long-term sustainability across multiple scientific domains, while the latter, highly effective for specific HEP use cases, has proven more challenging to generalise due to its complexity and limited adaptability over time. Future architectural choices will need to build on the strengths of loosely coupled approaches while carefully assessing where strongly coupled models remain justified by scientific need. Future systems must accommodate diverse computing architectures, different data types, and workflows that span facilities and domains. HPC sites typically prioritise tightly coupled, large-scale parallel jobs and worry that massive ensembles of short, data-driven tasks may overload shared services such as a Slurm database or undermine system efficiency. Conversely, data-intensive communities emphasise flexibility and high-throughput task execution.

Recent evaluations of the environmental impacts of the IT industry^{8,9} have shown that these are rapidly increasing in a context where absolute reduction is required to meet the Paris agreement¹⁰ on climate change and, more generally, to stay within the planetary boundaries. Worldwide, IT is responsible for as much GHG as twice Canada or 5.5 times France and its impacts amount to 40% of every connected individual's sustainable budgets. In France, it represents 11% of the total electricity consumption, 4.4% of the total GHG emissions distributed as 50% for terminals, 46% for datacentres and 4% for networks. These encompass significantly more than scientific IT infrastructures, with important contributions from the consumer market and the Cloud. The forthcoming increase in capacity must be carried out responsibly, that is sustainably, for the corresponding science to remain socially acceptable. This calls for an environmental management of the compute and data continuum described in this blueprint. Life-cycle analysis, from design to disposal, is prescribed to provide a systemic view, allow for balancing the impacts of the successive phases and reduce the total footprint. For existing systems this will account for realised impacts and guide usage, maintenance and end-of-life policies, while for future ones, it will allow trade-offs between capacity increase and footprint reduction to make the growth sustainable.

This Technical Blueprint outlines a framework for a European Compute and Data Continuum that integrates computational resources, data management systems, and orchestration into a set of interdependent capabilities supporting large-scale scientific discovery. The framework is based on input from the **SPECTRUM Community of Practice (SPECTRUMCoP)**, analysis of use cases from HEP and RA, and a review of existing European e-infrastructure, as well as existing recommendations for their eco-design.

Within this document, the compute and data continuum is defined as a collaborative system of systems that links data centres, HPC facilities, cloud and quantum technologies, networking, and scientific instruments into an interoperable ecosystem. It relies on shared interfaces, authentication, orchestration and monitoring to support cross-facility workflows.

It is important to recognise that the communities addressed by SPECTRUM encompass distinct categories of users, each with different operational needs and interaction patterns. These include long-tail scientists who require accessible, lightweight interfaces and opportunistic access; software developers and pipeline engineers responsible for adapting and optimising complex scientific workflows; and instrument and observatory operations teams whose priorities centre on reliability, sustained throughput, and predictable long-term resource commitments. Explicitly differentiating these user groups helps align technical solutions with their respective expectations and ensures that the Blueprint remains relevant across the full spectrum of scientific stakeholders.

This document represents the culmination of extensive collaborative effort involving leading European scientific organizations and infrastructure providers. The resulting framework provides both tactical

⁸ Impacts environnementaux du numérique dans le monde, third edition, Association Green IT, 2025 (EENM 2025)

⁹ Évaluation de l'impact environnemental du numérique en France, BRILLAND Thomas, FANGEAT Erwann, MEYER Julia, WELLHOFF Mathieu, ADEME 2025

¹⁰ <https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/the-paris-agreement>

guidance for near-term infrastructure decisions and strategic vision for long-term capability development that will enable breakthrough scientific discoveries across multiple domains while establishing European leadership in scientific computing.

1.2 Methodology

The development of this Technical Blueprint employed a comprehensive methodology that integrated community engagement, technical analysis, and strategic planning. The approach ensured that resulting recommendations reflect both current scientific requirements and future technological possibilities while remaining grounded in practical implementation considerations.

Community of Practice Engagement

The SPECTRUM Community of Practice (CoP) served as the primary vehicle for gathering input from the broader scientific community and infrastructure providers. Through a series of working groups focused on data management, workflow orchestration, computing environments, software tools, scientific use cases, and facilities management, the Community of Practice provided detailed feedback on current challenges and future requirements. The working groups conducted regular meetings throughout the project period, with participation from 65 experts representing diverse scientific domains and infrastructure providers across Europe.

A comprehensive survey administered to the CoP and extended networks captured quantitative data on resource utilization patterns, technical requirements, and policy preferences. The survey received around 75 substantive responses covering topics ranging from authentication and authorization preferences to energy efficiency concerns and emerging technology adoption plans. These responses, analyzed in the [SPECTRUM Deliverable D3.1](#), provided empirical grounding for many of the technical recommendations contained in this blueprint.

Analysis Framework for Technical Use Cases

A detailed analysis of 14 representative use cases spanning HEP experimental programs, RA observational campaigns, and emerging AI/ML applications in both domains was carried out. Each use case analysis followed a standardized framework examining scientific challenges, storage requirements, data transport needs, computational demands, workflow management approaches, access patterns, and gap identification.

The use case methodology enabled systematic comparison across different scientific applications, identification of common technical requirements, and assessment of how current infrastructure capabilities align with projected needs. The use cases ranged from mature production workloads from HEP experiments and RA instruments to the development, analysis and workloads of small teams or individual scientists. To enable the use of larger and more complex (distributed) systems, particular attention focused on scaling challenges, heterogeneous computing requirements, data lifecycle management needs, and workflow orchestration complexity that characterize next-generation scientific applications. The use cases are described in section 2.2.

Integration with previous SPECTRUM deliverables ensured consistency with access policy ([D5.2](#)), infrastructure landscape assessment ([D5.3](#)), use cases ([D5.1](#)), and the SPECTRUM CoP ([D3.1](#)). This integration enabled comprehensive understanding of both technical capabilities and operational frameworks necessary for effective scientific computing support.

Analysis Framework for Infrastructures

The methodology included systematic assessment of 20 European e-infrastructures representing HPC, HTC, cloud, and data-oriented platforms. Assessment criteria encompassed technical capabilities, access policies, operational practices, and strategic development plans. This comprehensive coverage enabled identification of current capability gaps, potential integration opportunities, and strategic development priorities.

Infrastructure assessment results informed both technical architecture recommendations and policy framework development. The analysis revealed significant diversity in technical approaches, access models, and operational practices that must be accommodated within federated infrastructure frameworks while enabling coherent user experiences and efficient resource utilization.

1.3 Related initiatives

Several European and international initiatives are tackling challenges that overlap with the objectives of SPECTRUM. While each has its own scope, together they provide important context and complementary efforts that inform the design of a European compute–data continuum.

In appendix B, we give a brief description of a non–exhaustive selection of the following initiatives, in no particular order.

- [JENA](#) (Joint ECFA–NuPECC–APPEC) Activities
- [InPex](#) (International Post–Exascale Project)
- [ETP4HPC](#)'s Transcontinuum Initiative (TCI)
- [EUCloudEdgeIoT and the OpenContinuum](#)
- [IPCEI–CIS](#) (Important Projects of Common European Interest – Cloud Infrastructure and Services)
- The [EuroHPC](#) Federation Platform (EFP)

Together, these initiatives highlight a shared direction toward federated, interoperable, and sovereign digital infrastructures. JENA demonstrates cross–domain collaboration within science, InPex offers a global research and policy perspective, TCI and OpenContinuum provide architectural blueprints for integration, IPCEI–CIS addresses sovereignty at industrial scale, and EFP tackles practical usability of EuroHPC systems. SPECTRUM's contribution is to bring the specific, large–scale needs of HEP and RA into this landscape, translating broad architectural visions into concrete requirements for scientific workflows, data volumes, and long–term sustainability. However, many of these capabilities are not yet technically implemented and where they are, they are often not interoperable with each other.

2. Preliminary work

The preliminary work carried out within SPECTRUM has provided the foundation for this Technical Blueprint. Through detailed analysis of representative use cases in HEP and RA, engagement with the Community of Practice, and alignment with existing European e-infrastructures, the project has identified key requirements, gaps, and opportunities for enabling a compute and data continuum. This work has not only clarified the technical challenges that must be addressed but has also highlighted commonalities across the two scientific domains, offering a pathway toward shared solutions for data intensive research. The findings presented here directly inform the design of the capability map (described in detail in the appendix), ensuring that the proposed continuum is grounded in real community needs. The subsections that follow describe the SPECTRUMCoP (2.1), examine the current landscape and its gaps (2.2), describe representative use cases from HEP and RA (2.3), and analyse the requirements for interoperable access policies (2.4).

2.1 The SPECTRUM Community of Practice

This section reports WP3 and WP4 activity describing the setup and outputs of the SPECTRUMCoP, the Knowledge Hub, the domain-wide survey and a first set of findings and directions that will feed into the Technical Blueprint and the Strategic Research, Innovation & Deployment Agenda (SRIDA).

SPECTRUM WP3 established a Community of Practice to gather informed, cross-domain input (primarily HEP and RA, extended to related domains) on future compute and data needs for exabyte-scale science. The CoP is intended to remain an active, post-project forum to support alignment between research communities and e-Infrastructures and to provide the evidence base for SPECTRUM deliverables (Blueprint, SRIDA). After the conclusion of WP3 in March 2025, WP4 took over the responsibility of the CoP.

2.1.1 Organisation of the CoP

The CoP was organised into six Working Groups (WGs) covering Data Management & Access; Workflow Management & Organisation; Compute Environment; Software Tools; Scientific Use Cases; and Facilities. WG chairs were appointed (project-funded contributors where available) to coordinate activity.

The CoP attracted significant engagement: at launch (June 2024) ~76 subscriptions (~56 unique participants), growing to ~65 unique participants and >119 WG subscriptions by early 2025. Regular plenary meetings and WG-level meetings were the primary modes of activity.

SPECTRUM aligned closely with other community initiatives (JENA, WLCG, ESCAPE/Open Collaboration, and SKA SRCNet) to avoid duplication, share survey design, and foster common inputs to community roadmaps (notably the European Strategy for Particle Physics update).

2.1.2 The Knowledge Hub

The Knowledge Hub is a Confluence-based repository and coordination space for WG outputs, meeting minutes, and curated community documents. It was chosen for familiarity and integration with existing EGI hosting rather than newer community platforms.

The repository collects templates and metadata for documents and holds more than 60 curated documents spanning experiment roadmaps, technical reports, conference papers and policy inputs. Most activity contributing to the Hub has come from SPECTRUM members during synchronous meetings rather than asynchronous edits. The Hub is explicitly intended to inform the Technical Blueprint and SRIDA.

2.1.3 The Survey

A single, multi-section survey was developed to cover the domains of the WGs while minimising burden on respondents and ensuring GDPR compliance; the EU Survey platform (EC tool) was selected to host the questionnaire. Sections include respondent profile, authentication & authorisation, computing & data needs, compute environment, software & careers, use cases and e-Infrastructure offerings. The survey was designed to present only relevant question blocks to each respondent, using conditional branching, and to allow document uploads and staged completion.

2.1.4 Findings

This subsection summarizes the findings from the knowledge hub and the survey.

Career and skills

A recurring concern is the shortage of stable career paths for domain-specific software and data engineers; many respondents cited the risk that personnel will migrate to industry, threatening capacity to design and operate the large systems required in the coming decade. The report flags this as requiring high-level domain attention.

Software evolution

There is a consistent call to modernise software stacks to exploit heterogeneous architectures (multicore, vector units, GPUs, FPGAs) and to improve portability and performance. This includes emphasis on parallelisation, portability strategies and tooling.

Artificial Intelligence

AI/ML is regarded as a foundational technology to be integrated across software ecosystems (both as user tools and for optimisation), and the community expects growing dependence on AI over the next 5–10 years.

FAIR, open and cross-domain collaboration

The report emphasises adherence to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) for data and software, and recommends closer inter- and extra-domain collaboration (e.g., through shared repositories, standards and common toolchains) to avoid siloing.

Cloud, HPC and virtualization

The community recognises an increasing role for HPC and cloud resources. Surveyed e-Infrastructure providers report support for virtualization, and the network filesystem [CVMFS](#) is widely supported as a distribution method, a favourable trend for deployment portability.

Network and node connectivity

A persistent technical constraint identified is network connectivity from compute nodes (external networking). While many centres indicate willingness/ability to enable needed connectivity and bandwidth, the report notes that promised capability must be validated against realistic use cases.

Resource allocation duration

Respondents highlighted the need for longer-term resource allocations to enable sustained workflows (rather than short, months-scale grants); the survey indicates that longer allocations are possible in many centres, but the report flags a policy and funding engagement need with infrastructure funders to secure such arrangements.

2.2 Landscape, Requirements and Gap Analysis

This section considers the [SPECTRUM D5.3](#) report on "**Landscape of RIs: technologies, services, gaps**", which surveys the technical characteristics of 20 European e-Infrastructures supporting research communities and data-intensive applications with significant computing requirements, particularly with High Energy Physics (HEP) and Radio Astronomy (RA) use cases. SPECTRUM D5.3 identifies gaps and proposes recommendations for the future evolution of Europe's e-Infrastructure landscape. The [Deliverable D5.3](#) is aligned with the recommendations provided in the companion [SPECTRUM Deliverable D5.2](#) (Interoperable Access Policies: Analysis and Recommendations).

2.2.1 European e-infrastructure landscape

The infrastructures studied span High Performance Computing (HPC), High Throughput Computing (HTC), dedicated Data-oriented infrastructures, and Cloud e-Infrastructures.

- **HPC-oriented infrastructures**

The [EuroHPC Joint Undertaking \(JU\)](#) forms the backbone of this landscape, comprising operational petascale systems¹¹ such as [Deucalion](#), [Discoverer](#), [Karolina](#), [Leonardo](#), [LUMI](#), [MareNostrum 5](#), [Meluxina](#) and [Vega](#), with exascale systems [JUPITER](#) (Germany), [Arrhenius](#) (Sweden), [Daedalus](#) (Greece) and [Alice Recoque](#) (France) planned for 2025-26. National centres such as [ICSC](#) (Italy), [GCS/JSC/HLRS/LRZ/NHR Alliance](#) (Germany), [RES](#) (Spain), [CSCS](#) (Switzerland), [EPCC](#) (UK) and [GENCI](#) (France) complement these resources and will support future HEP and RA experiments.

- **HTC-oriented infrastructures**

The [WLCG](#) serves the global HEP community with about 1.4 million CPU cores and 1.5 Exabytes of storage (2025). WLCG Tier-1 centers, the [EGI HTC-oriented infrastructure](#) provide access for diverse scientific communities, together with upcoming HTC platforms that include regional centres such as the [SKA facility](#).

- **Data-oriented infrastructures**

They include the WLCG's data lake (across the world and with CERN in Switzerland as the central hub), the [SKA SRCNet](#), the [EBRAINS neuroscience platform](#), the [LOFAR Long-Term Archive \(LTA\)](#), German's [ErUM4 Data Hub](#), the [ICSC National Center](#) in Italy, the [PUNCH4NFDI](#) initiative and the [Copernicus Earth-observation data space](#).

- **Cloud-oriented infrastructures**

In contrast to the three categories of infrastructures above, Cloud-oriented e-Infrastructures often provide a combination of compute (HTC and increasingly HPC) and data services. This category include for example: the [EGI FedCloud](#), which offers a federated cloud interface that unifies resources across Europe; [SURF's Grid](#) and [Spider](#) platforms mix cloud and HTC/HPC services the [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\) Federation](#), which federates national nodes and thematic pilots (the first 13 pilot nodes were announced in March 2025¹²) and the [Simpl Data Federation Platform](#), built under a commercial contract for the European Commission, which aims at unifying access to diverse European data spaces.

2.2.2 Landscape, best practices and gaps

This section derives technical and operational requirements for future e-Infrastructures. The requirements for use cases identified in [Deliverable D5.1](#) (Representative use cases: analysis and alignment) and submitted via the [SpectrumCoP](#) have been analyzed, and the results are included in this section. To ensure consistency, the study defined a template covering five key aspects:

- **Storage/Data Capabilities and Services**, detailed in section [2.2.1.1](#).
- **Data Transfer and Federation**, detailed in section [2.2.1.2](#).
- **Compute Capabilities and Services**, detailed in section [2.2.1.3](#).
- **Software Services, Interfaces and Stacks**, detailed in section [2.2.1.4](#).
- **Compute Federation Services**, detailed in section [2.2.1.5](#).

2.2.2.1 Storage/Data Capabilities and Services

Requirement #1: FAIR storage for observation/experiment data across domains

Across data-intensive scientific domains, agree on common interfaces and core implementation for e-Infrastructures that preserve observation/experiment data (including meta- and provenance data) and make it available to scientists and the public according to the FAIR principles.

The key requirement for such an architecture and implemented core components is to preserve the vast and rapidly growing amounts of observation/experiment data together with the relevant metadata and provenance information according to the FAIR principles. The capability to search for and locate data based on provenance and contents, and the ability to interoperate seamlessly with HTC and HPC infrastructures, will be other key requirements..

Considerations (Requirement #1)

- Long-term storage of irreplaceable observation/experiment data is a key requirement across HEP, RA and many other science domains – efforts like [WLCG](#), [LOFAR LTA](#) and [SRCNet](#) demonstrate how this can be done.

¹¹ https://www.eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/supercomputers/our-supercomputers_en

¹² <https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/pilots>

- The number of data-intensive research communities and the data volume is increasing sharply, with issues to get access to needed storage volumes
- Common interfaces or core implementation for storing/providing experiment/observation data and provenance/metadata could leverage economies of scale and avoid duplication of work.
- Efficient interfaces to HPC and/or HTC infrastructures needs to be incorporated to enable seamless work across heterogeneous systems.
- The hard requirement to support international, non-EU researchers raises policy and technical issues.

Requirement #2: Appropriate provision must be made for data covered by the GDPR or other restrictions

Scientific domains in life sciences, medicine require storing and processing of personally identifiable data in an e-Infrastructure; it will be required to optimise and standardise the technical implementation to support EC (and national) regulations (e.g., GDPR) effectively for different scientific use cases.

Considerations (Requirement #2)

- Storing and processing sensitive (in particular special category) data or commercially valuable/sensitive data requires stringent data protection (policies and technical means).
- Technical measures include encryption of data at rest/in transit/in memory, secure & fine-grained management of keys and access rights, extensive logging, vetting/validation of applications and audit capabilities.
- Care has to be taken when integrating support for storing and processing personal and in particular special category data with an open science based FAIR data storage/provisioning system; the strict protection rules and limitations for such data should not be applied to fully open scientific data, performance loss and additional energy used for string encryption should be avoided for the open data, and no restrictions should be imposed on applications working on open data (as is often the case for special category data).
- Potentially, extra security layers may be added (e.g. secure sandboxes). Viability of standard tools for data anonymisation or pseudonymisation should be investigated.

2.2.2.2 Data Transfer and Federation

Requirement #3: Automated, efficient data movement and data staging

Data movement and data staging between storage solutions within a single site, between sites in an e-Infrastructure, or between federated e-Infrastructures (such as between data storage and HTC/HPC systems) should be handled automatically and rapidly.

Considerations (Requirement #3)

- Data staging/transfer is often performed in job scripts/workflow steps using low-level and centre-provided/specific tools, complicating coding, maintenance and use.
- Highly efficient, multi-stream transfer methods are not universally adopted by e-Infrastructures yet.
- Standard interfaces to express data transfer to be automatically mapped to specific tools/protocols would address this – an example is [FTS](#) as used by [WLCG/EGI](#).
- Large transfers need to be scheduled externally from the sending and receiving sites. The capability for third party transfers is essential in large scale data management.
- Automated data transfer into/out of HPC centers will impact the security architecture and configuration of (HPC) centres.

Requirement #4: Plan data transfer capacity according to research community requirements

For future HPC e-Infrastructures, the evolving needs of research communities should drive the planning of data transfer and ephemeral storage capacities. Compute and long-term storage are usually planned more explicitly, while transient data movement and short-lived storage needs tend to scale unpredictably with workflow complexity, making them more sensitive to community-driven changes.

Considerations (Requirement #4)

- Capacity and performance of data transfer into/out of HPC/HTC centers must fit the demand.
- Data transfer requirements will likely evolve across the lifetime of expensive HPC and HTC resources; hence, the centers must be prepared for evolving their initial policies according to user needs.

2.2.2.3 Compute Capabilities and Services

Requirement #5: Enable portability of compute tasks across accelerated compute platforms

Enable compute tasks used by research communities to run across different families/vendors of accelerated compute resources, helping avoid unnecessary transfers and duplication when switching between vendors and improving overall efficiency.

Considerations (Requirement #5)

- Accelerator (mainly GPU) capacity has been vastly increased by HPC infrastructures.
- Portability of codes between different HW accelerators is impacted by the proprietary nature of the CUDA SW ecosystem.
- Portability to other classes of accelerators (such as FPGAs) is difficult for fundamental reasons; for example, FPGAs use spatial parallelism, have no fixed instruction set, rely on deeply customized memory layouts, and require hardware-level design flows. These traits make automatic portability from GPU/CPU code inherently difficult.
- Portable programming models or portability layers for GPUs do exist, examples include [Kokkos](#), [Alpaka](#), [SYCL](#), and [oneAPI](#), and high-level AI environments, such as [PyTorch](#) and [TensorFlow](#), show how backend optimisations can be made transparent to end-users.

2.2.2.4 Software Services, Interfaces, and Stacks

Requirement #6: Establish common workflow systems supported by all e-Infrastructures

Identify a number of workflow systems covering the needs of key research communities and ensure support by e-Infrastructures.

Considerations (Requirement #6)

- There is no shortage of different workflow systems (for encoding workflows and orchestrating them), including general (e.g., LOFAR pipelines, PanDA, Rucio), and domain-specific frameworks.
- HPC and HTC centers must provide interfaces to support orchestration of workflows.
- Supporting multiple workflow systems for different communities creates overhead and duplicated work (one example is the [WLCG HTCondor](#)-based workflows versus [LEXIS](#) for the [EuroHPC JU federation platform](#)).
- Judicious collaboration and co-design between providers and scientific communities could reduce the set of workflow systems in a first step, and then ideally agree on a small number (ideally one) of systems across domains, and the time saved through such convergence could be re-invested in optimising how workflows map onto the infrastructure.
- External API access to the internal batch system in HPC centers would allow decoupling the workflow system from the one used in the fabric (typically Slurm).

Requirement #7: Establish common SW stacks for compute applications

Establish common SW stacks for research communities deployed on the relevant e-Infrastructures.

Considerations (Requirement #7)

- Similar to requirement #8 in [D5.2](#), common SW interfaces across different HW architectures and system configurations would simplify the life of end-users.
- Here, focus is more on how to manage virtualisation techniques (mainly containers) to provide specific, optimised stacks for combinations of CPUs, interconnect networks and accelerators (e.g., GPUs).

2.2.2.5 Compute Federation Services

The use cases studied in detail in D5.1 do not explicitly require federation of compute resources in any specific way. The [EuroHPC JU Federation Platform](#) is introducing an AARC-BPA-compliant AAI, enabling the use of institutional identities via eduGAIN across EuroHPC systems, along with interoperable (or federated) services for cross-site workflows and simplified, common interfaces for the use of the HPC systems, following previous initiatives like [FENIX](#) and Grid Computing platforms. Other HPC e-Infrastructures, such as [CSCS](#) and [GENCI](#), provide similar federation capabilities between their constituent sites/systems. It should be mentioned that none of these support end user access privileges/quotas across all participating systems, and that automatic routing of accesses/compute tasks to the best suited systems is not available.

As mentioned in [D5.3](#), [WLCG](#) federates its HTC resources for workflow execution; this is currently done via an experiment specific layer, with centers providing an access point to internal resources (usually mediated by a batch system). The [EGI federation](#) provides a brokering service for scientific end-users and makes access to public and commercial providers of OpenStack Cloud resources ([EGI Federated Cloud](#)) federated via a common AAI, accounting and image repository. [Simpl](#) (Smart Middleware Platform) is a secure middleware SW platform, procured by the EC, that supports federated data access and interoperability in European sectoral data spaces which is still in the early stages of development; a first “minimum viable product” (MVP) version was released at the end of January 2025 with this functionality:

- Onboarding of users by the governance authority.
- Catalogues for infrastructure & data, usage policies, and quality rules.
- UI and API for adding to the catalogues and for validating entries.
- UI and API for basic and extended searches within a single data space.
- Resource selection, request to use that resource, and establish a basic contract between the data provider and the consumer.
- Infrastructure deployment, data set access, and initial types of data processing.
- Secure communication between Simpl agents, logging of basic metrics for all user actions.

The first release and deployment of Simpl-Labs is expected for 2025 with important capabilities (such as support/ticketing/helpdesk, HPC integration, data analytics) in service until the end of 2026.

2.3 Representative use cases

This section provides a very brief overview of the SPECTRUM D5.1 report on “**Representative use cases: analysis and alignment**,” which analyzes data-intensive scientific workflows from HEP, RA and elsewhere to inform the development of a European compute and data continuum for the Exascale era. The report analyzed thirteen representative use cases to identify current and future requirements in the areas of compute resources, data storage/processing capabilities, and essential services. The resulting analysis identifies cross-cutting requirements across the use cases as well as their potential impact on other areas of science.

For details on the selected use cases, please refer to [SPECTRUM Deliverable D.5.1](#). Here we simply list the experiments and use cases that were studied.

High Energy Physics Use Cases

The four major WLCG/LHC experiments:

- [CMS](#)
- [ATLAS](#)
- [LHCb](#)
- [ALICE](#)

Selected AI Applications in HEP:

- AI-based particle flow reconstruction^{13 14 15 16}
- LLMs for the CERN accelerator complex¹⁷

¹³ Pata, J., Duarte, J., Vlimant, JR. et al. MLPF: efficient machine-learned particle-flow reconstruction using graph neural networks. Eur. Phys. J. C 81, 381 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjc/s10052-021-09158-w>

¹⁴Machine Learning for Particle Flow Reconstruction at CMS, Joosep Pata et al 2023 J. Phys.: Conf. Ser. 2438 012100 (2023), doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2438/1/012100

¹⁵Pata, J., Wulff, E., Mokhtar, F. et al. Improved particle-flow event reconstruction with scalable neural networks for current and future particle detectors. Commun Phys 7, 124 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42005-024-01599-5>

¹⁶Fine-tuning machine-learned particle-flow reconstruction for new detector geometries in future colliders Farouk Mokhtar et al. Phys. Rev. D 111, 092015 (2025) <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.111.092015>

¹⁷AccGPT: A CERN Knowledge Retrieval Chatbot, Florian Rehm et al. EPJ Web of Conferences 337, 01279 (2025) <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202533701279>

There are numerous other AI- and ML-based algorithms and applications in HEP^{18 19 20 21 22}.

Radio Astronomy Use Cases

SKA Observatory (SKAO):

- **SRCNet** and 21 cm HI Fluctuations
- Star Formation History

Other Radio Astronomy Initiatives:

- **LOFAR** Extragalactic Surveys
- Fast Radio Bursts and Transients

Other Related Use Cases

- **MISTRAL** (Meteo Italian Supercomputing Portal)
- **LIGATE** Molecular Dynamics
- Simulation of plastic neural networks in the brain

2.3.1 Key Findings and Recommendations

The key recommendations and findings as reported in **SPECTRUM Deliverable D.5.1** are as follows.

1. Unprecedented Data Growth: Both HEP and RA communities are entering an era of steep growth in data generation that will exceed current infrastructure capabilities.
2. Heterogeneous Computing Evolution: there is a clear trend toward mixed CPU/GPU environments, with growing importance of specialized AI hardware.
3. Complex Workflow Requirements: Advanced workflow management systems are needed to orchestrate multi-step processes across distributed resources.
4. Data Federation Essentials: Robust data federation mechanisms are required to support efficient discovery, access, and transfer across multiple sites.
5. Resource Planning Horizons: Multi-year allocations for storage and compute are needed to enable better integration of HPC resources into long-term scientific planning.
6. Standardization Needs: Common facility standards and implementation of these standards would reduce costs and complexity of future integrations.
7. Authentication Evolution: Authentication and authorization systems must be federated and evolve to balance security requirements with the need for automation.

The report concludes that addressing these challenges is essential for maintaining Europe's position at the forefront of scientific discovery. The SPECTRUM project aims to guide this evolution by fostering an ecosystem that enables groundbreaking scientific discoveries in the Exascale era.

The findings demonstrate that next-generation scientific infrastructure must support diverse computing paradigms simultaneously, with flexible architectures capable of handling heterogeneous workloads. Data management systems must scale to exabyte levels while providing seamless access across distributed environments. Perhaps most importantly, closer collaboration between scientific communities can lead to more efficient resource utilization and accelerated innovation in shared tools and methodologies.

¹⁸ A Living Review of Machine Learning for High Energy Physics, <https://iml-wg.github.io/HEPML-LivingReview/>

¹⁹ Machine Learning in High Energy Physics Community White Paper, Kim Albertsson et al 2018 J. Phys.: Conf. Ser. 1085 022008, doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1085/2/022008

²⁰ [R.L. Workman et al. \(Particle Data Group\), Prog. Theor. Exp. Phys. 2022, 083C01 \(2022\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/2203.04732) and 2023 update, <https://pdg.lbl.gov/2023/reviews/rpp2023-rev-machine-learning.pdf>

²¹ Review of Machine Learning for Real-Time Analysis at the Large Hadron Collider experiments ALICE, ATLAS, CMS and LHCb, Laura Boggia et al. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2506.14578>

²² Mondal, S., Mastrolorenzo, L. Machine learning in high energy physics: a review of heavy-flavor jet tagging at the LHC. Eur. Phys. J. Spec. Top. 233, 2657–2686 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjs/s11734-024-01234-y>

2.4 Interoperable access policies

This section considers the [SPECTRUM D5.2](#) report on "**Interoperable access policies: analysis and recommendations**", which presents the results of an in-depth study on existing and proposed access policies for European e-Infrastructures, supporting research communities and data-intensive applications with substantial computing needs.

2.4.1 Categories of e-Infrastructures Studied

The services provided by e-Infrastructures roughly fall into several categories:

- **High-Performance Computing/HPC-oriented**
E-Infrastructures designed to run closely-coupled applications/workflows with a high degree of parallelism (large compute capabilities, designed for large-scale, tightly coupled parallel applications running on a large number of nodes of a supercomputer).
- **High Throughput Computing/HTC-oriented**
E-Infrastructures target running a large number of tasks at the same time, which themselves have only a low degree of parallelism (significant compute capacity, oriented towards high throughput of large numbers of applications each running on one or a small number of nodes in a datacenter).
- **Data-oriented**
E-Infrastructures provide access to input data for scientific use and storage space for results data (mid/long-term storage for and access to significant volumes of data).
- **Cloud e-Infrastructures**
Non-commercial Cloud e-infrastructure provide a combination of compute (HTC and increasingly HPC) and data services (variety of compute and data services across multiple operational locations, use of Cloud interfaces and abstractions).

2.4.2 Access Policies, Gaps and Recommendations

This section presents the analysis results for the set of selected e-Infrastructures listed above. The content is derived from information made available online via the Web presences or service portals maintained by the e-Infrastructures covered, as well as published in papers and presentations, or obtained through direct communication with e-Infrastructure providers. The access policies analysis and the methods are based on the following common template:

- **Obtaining Access**
- **Access Tracks and Modalities**
- **Summary of Accessible Resources**
- **Access Management and Security**
- **Rules and Assurances / Monitoring, Evaluation, and Evolution**

Obtaining Access

From the analysis of access policies, two distinct methods of handling access requests and providing access emerge:

- Allocating resources according to the result of reviewing a specific access proposal according to the rules of the resource provider or of the organisation responsible for a resource call-for-proposal, which focus on scientific merit and novelty, and often require a peer review. Access is granted for a specified period (usually one year or less, in some cases two years), and extension proposals are typically supported by most providers. Otherwise, the mechanism is designed to disallow repetitive access proposals, and in some cases, it also restricts principal investigators (PIs) from submitting multiple different access proposals.
- Based on the agreement between a research community and an e-Infrastructure, and in some cases involving a third party as a broker, access is provided to scientists based on their demonstrated membership in that research community. The allocation period can be an arbitrary amount of time, and entitlement lapses when the scientist leaves the research community (or "virtual organisation").

Gap #1: *Long-term assured access and planning of resource allocations:*

- Grant-based access is limited in time (1-2 years) and based on scientific excellence of specific access proposals.
- Grants can often be extended, yet this is not guaranteed and hence problematic for long term planning.

- Use cases need guaranteed access for longer time periods (3–5 years), compatible with the long range planning and funding cycles appropriate for these experiments.

***Recommendation #1²³:** Adopt longer-term, flexible resource allocation processes.*

***Gap #2:** Resource allocations that are valid across a single e-Infrastructure:*

- In many cases (such as EuroHPC JU), allocations are good for specific hosting sites/systems only.
- Users (in the CoP) have voiced desire to use resources across an e-Infrastructure: burst capacity, efficiency of systems for parts of their workload, resiliency.
- The resource provider's point of view needs to be accommodated.

***Recommendation #2:** Enable e-Infrastructure-wide use of resource allocations and quotas.*

Access Tracks and Modalities

Traditionally, HPC and HTC centers focus on batch processing, governed by a scheduling/orchestration system like Slurm. Here, end-users submit job scripts (containing the amount and type of compute resources required), which are run at a time determined by the scheduling system in unattended mode. This approach enables the efficient use of available HPC resources and is well-suited to large-scale parallel jobs. Interactive access is possible in two ways: via special head or login nodes (potentially competing with other users) or sets of (partial) nodes allocated via the batch system (with exclusive access).

***Gap #3:** Interactive access to significant-scale computing resources:*

- Problems include delays in availability (due to scheduling), and potential underuse of resources (in batch scenarios).
- Compromise to be reached between quick availability, performance guarantees and efficient use of resources.

***Recommendation #3:** Extend scheduling/orchestration to support on-demand interactive compute use cases with access to sizable nodes.*

***Gap #4:** High-level end-user interfaces – essentially science platforms:*

- Most e-Infrastructures do not offer high-level, abstracted interfaces for common application/workloads; for example, like LOFAR pipeline portals or HEP systems like PanDA, which let users run complex workflows without dealing with scheduler flags, modules, or environment setup.
- Domain scientists should not need to fiddle with system details and brittle application interfaces, such as low-level scheduler options, module setups, environment conflicts, or fragile command-line tools.

***Recommendation #4:** Introduce high-level general and domain-specific user interfaces.*

Access Management and Security

Common mechanisms used by the studied e-Infrastructures include using password-protected certificates/keys (such as SSL key pairs) provided by the end-user, or relying on tokens or time-limited keys provided by a central single-sign-on service (which in turn uses userid/password or certificate/key authentication). Due to security concerns, centers have started to enforce multi-factor authentication (MFA), which involves an “interactive” authentication step involving a resource (such as a mobile phone) in the possession of the end user and the end user him/herself. For the widely adopted authentication method using SSH key pairs, end-users can avoid repeatedly entering the private key password, for instance, by keeping an initial connection open for a full session or by automating the password entry using Linux mechanisms. Unfortunately, this creates security vulnerabilities, particularly for the second example, which would require the storage of cleartext passwords on file or in memory.

***Gap #5:** Adoption and lack of federation of end-user identities (also across e-Infrastructures):*

- Federated e-Infrastructures abstract from local user identities.
- End-users working across different federated e-Infrastructures would profit from common identities/AAI systems across the different infrastructures²⁴.

***Recommendation #5:** Introduce common and interoperable AAI services across European e-Infrastructures with support for service accounts.*

***Gap #6:** Unattended execution of long-running workflows and services:*

²³R#1 is also supported by the recent [ESFRI landscape study](#).

²⁴For example, proposed by AARC – <https://aarc-community.org/aarc-tree-project/>.

- Increasing reliance on MFA-based authentication methods, which do not support the scenario of unattended workflows running for days/weeks, introduce the need for re-authentication (manual or automatic).
- Access privileges handed out after interactive or MFA authentication have a limited period of validity (often one day).
- After that period, workflow steps would need to interactively re-authenticate.

Recommendation #6: *Ensure Reliable and Unattended execution of long-running workflows.*

Rules and Assurances / Monitoring, Evaluation, and Evolution

All studied e-Infrastructures require their end users to comply with acceptable use policies; while they differ in detail across the infrastructures, they contain a core of rules banning malicious behaviour (which would impact the operation and/or other end users), oversubscription of scarce resources (such as access or login nodes, or flooding a batch system with jobs), and use for commercial purposes (unless explicitly approved). In general the e-Infrastructures give “best effort” assurances regarding availability and operation of their resources, and don’t accept liability for direct or consequential damages caused, for instance, by non-availability of services, technical or operational faults, or activities of their personnel.

System and center operators all monitor and evaluate the performance of their local infrastructure in site-specific ways. This includes uptime, incidence of faults, utilization of compute, storage, and network resources, as well as usage statistics derived from end-user and project accounting. This data informs the operation of resources/sites (such as the scheduling of maintenance or the incremental addition of resources), and it forms the basis for justifying public funding received from funding authorities or projects/communities. The key observation is that such measures are handled in a site-specific (and often non-public) way for most of the studied e-Infrastructures.

Gap #7: *Efficient provision of standard, low-level SW interfaces across different (accelerator) systems:*

- SW environments differ considerably between e-Infrastructures (often even between different sites), in particular if performance/efficiency is a prime concern.
- Standardised SW stacks with scalable SW distribution and efficient build system have been proposed / are available (such as Easybuild and Spack), in addition to containers.
- Need widespread agreement on a set of commonly provided low-level SW interfaces for application portability and effective ways to support different (accelerator) systems.

Recommendation #7: *Provision efficient standard, low-level SW interfaces.*

Gap #8: *Organised feedback/improvement/planning loop:*

- Organised and effective collaboration on co-designing and improving e-Infrastructures is happening in places (such as [WLCG](#) and [SRCNet](#)), yet is not common.
- Rolling such schemes out between all relevant end-user communities and e-Infrastructures would improve planning and help to ensure good support of end-users.

Recommendation #8: *Establish feedback/improvement/planning loops for research communities and e-Infrastructures.*

2.5 Consolidated Gaps/Requirements and Recommendations

This section summarizes the gaps, requirements and recommendations found in sections 2.1 to 2.3. Some of the gaps and recommendations from the previous sections are similar and have been merged for clarity. The fact that similar gaps have been identified in different places show that these requirements are grounded in the real needs of the HEP and RA communities and that these communities share many challenges and opportunities.

Table 1 summarizes and numbers the gaps/requirements identified during the first phase of the SPECTRUM project and briefly describes the project consortium’s recommendation. It also indicates from where the gap/requirement was identified by pointing to the subsection in section 2 where it was covered. Finally it also indicates which capabilities in the Compute and Data Continuum capability map that are involved in implementing each recommendation. The capability map is described in detail in the appendix.

Table 1: Consolidated gaps/requirements and recommendations from the study of the landscape of RIs, use cases from HEP, RA and beyond, as well as interoperable access policies.

#	Gap/Requirement	Recommendation	Source Section	Capability
1	Long-term resource provisioning Current grant-based allocations are short (1–2 years) and fragmented by site; HEP and RA need assured access on decadal timescales.	Establish long-term (3–5 year) flexible allocation frameworks, federated across infrastructures, with transparent accounting and monitoring. Policy activity will require dedicated funding.	2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4	Resource Federation, Operational Sustainability
2	Federated access and identity management End-users face fragmented identity systems across e-infrastructures, complicating multi-site workflows. Authentication often interrupts unattended, long-running jobs.	Deploy interoperable AAI frameworks across European e-infrastructures, supporting single sign-on, attribute-based authorization, and persistent tokens for long workflows.	2.2, 2.4	Security & Trust, Resource Federation
3	Interoperable allocation and accounting Allocations and quotas are bound to specific HPC centers, limiting flexibility. Accounting practices differ across infrastructures.	Enable e-infrastructure-wide allocations and harmonized accounting, so projects can burst across systems and providers while ensuring fair contributions and usage transparency.	2.2, 2.3, 2.4	Resource Federation, Operational Sustainability
4	High-level and portable software environments Software stacks differ widely between sites; portability across CPUs, GPUs, and accelerators is inconsistent. Scientists often face brittle interfaces.	Provide standardized, efficient software stacks (containers, CVMFS) and high-level domain-specific interfaces, enabling reproducibility and accelerator portability.	2.1, 2.2, 2.3	Software & Execution, Compute Continuum
5	Workflow execution and orchestration Workflow engines are fragmented across communities (e.g. HTCondor in HEP vs. LEXIS in EuroHPC). Cross-facility workflows lack resilience and provenance capture.	Co-design and converge on a set of common APIs for workflow systems, with support for unattended execution, provenance tracking, and cross-infrastructure orchestration.	2.2, 2.3	Orchestration & Workflows, Software & Execution
6	Data federation and FAIR principles No unified approach to FAIR storage, metadata, and provenance across domains; irreplaceable datasets risk fragmentation.	Establish interoperable federated data management with FAIR-compliant storage, metadata catalogs, and efficient interfaces to HPC/HTC, ensuring long-term access and reproducibility.	2.1 2.2, 2.3	Data Continuum, Operational Sustainability
7	Data transfer and staging Data movement across sites often relies on ad-hoc scripts and site-specific tools; transfer capacity planning is uneven.	Automate large-scale, third-party enabled, efficient data movement with standardized protocols, and plan data transfer/storage capacity jointly with community needs.	2.2, 2.3	Data Continuum, Compute Continuum

#	Gap/Requirement	Recommendation	Source Section	Capability
8	<p>Real-time and low-latency processing</p> <p>A small number of RA use cases (e.g. transient detection) and some HEP triggers require near-real-time data analysis via pipelines.</p>	Extend continuum capabilities with real-time, low-latency processing.	2.3	Compute Continuum, Real-time & Low-Latency Computing
9	<p>Security, privacy, and sensitive data handling</p> <p>Personal or commercially sensitive data requires stronger safeguards; GDPR compliance adds complexity.</p>	Provide flexible architectures: robust encryption, key management, auditing, anonymization/pseudo-anonymization, and possibly separate high-protection infrastructure paths.	2.2, 2.4	Security & Trust, Data Continuum
10	<p>Monitoring and observability</p> <p>Current infrastructures lack consistent, cross-site monitoring of workflows, performance, and energy usage.</p>	Deploy monitoring and observability frameworks that capture standardized metrics describing infrastructure health, application performance, provenance, and sustainability.	2.3	Monitoring & Observability, Operational Sustainability
11	<p>AI/ML integration</p> <p>AI/ML workloads are increasingly central and are being investigated in every step of the data-processing pipelines, from data-acquisition to simulation and analysis.</p>	Enhance services in AI/ML platforms to support distributed training, inference deployment, and access to foundation models, integrated with HPC and domain workflows.	2.1 2.2, 2.3	Advanced Analytics & AI/ML, Software Distribution & Execution
12	<p>Co-design and feedback loops</p> <p>Systematic co-design between science communities and infrastructure providers is patchy; planning often mismatches user needs.</p>	Establish structured feedback loops (like WLCG/SRCNet) across domains, embedding co-design in infrastructure roadmaps, procurement, and evaluation.	2.1 2.2, 2.3, 2.4	Operational Sustainability, Resource Federation
13	<p>Workforce for scientific software development, funding, and sustainability</p> <p>Long-term sustainability depends on stable funding, governance, and skilled personnel. Current models are fragmented.</p>	Develop coordinated European funding/governance models, align with national contributions, and invest in training and career pathways for research software engineers and data stewards.	2.1 2.2, 2.3	Operational Sustainability
14	<p>Interactive access to significant-scale computing</p> <p>Interactive access to small/medium partitions is possible. Problems include delays in availability, and potential underuse of resources.</p>	Extend scheduling/orchestration to support interactive compute use cases (incl. those that have significant resource needs) Compromise to be reached between quick availability, performance guarantees and efficient use of resources.	2.4	Compute Continuum, Orchestration and Workflows
15	<p>High-level end-user interfaces</p>	Introduce high-level general and domain-specific user interfaces.	2.4	Software Distribution &

#	Gap/Requirement	Recommendation	Source Section	Capability
	Most e-Infrastructures do not offer high-level, abstracted interfaces. Domain scientists should not need to know system details and interact with brittle application interfaces.	(like workflow portals, Jupyter, or CARTA)		Execution, Orchestration & Workflows
16	<p>Unattended execution of long-running workflows and services</p> <p>Two-factor authentication can impact execution of long-running workflows and services. Access established after interactive or MFA authentication has a limited period of validity. Workflow steps need to interactively re-authenticate.</p>	Ensure reliable and unattended execution of long-running workflows and user-operated services.	2.4	Orchestration & Workflows, Security & Trust

3. Sustainability

Sustainability is central to large research infrastructures like those of HEP and RA because of their long lifetimes. The corresponding science should also be reproducible while the intellectual, technical and financial investments must build on the existing knowledge base for the next generation. For IT-related aspects, this translates into data and software preservation, which favours reuse and open science, and also into environmental sustainability of the compute and storage infrastructure. Transverse to these are qualities related to efficiency, quality and flexibility which together allow for achieving the desired results with fewer or variable resources. The latter depends on the expertise of the teams and a fine understanding of what is at stake, which results from gathering experience and critically depends on a sustainable workforce.

3.1 Data and software preservation and reuse

Significant efforts are currently devoted to building data and software archives, however their uses are often limited to a single community or even groups in such communities. This is one of the causes of the reproducibility crisis that science is currently experiencing. Facilitating reuse of both the data and the software would yield a number of benefits starting with sounder science, more thorough understanding of the data as successive analyses would allow for interpreting an increased fraction of the information it contains and improvement of the software in terms of coverage and robustness through independent testing. These are the drivers for FAIR data management and Open Science and support sustainability in the sense that science becomes increasingly trustable, the effort for producing it is reduced as more science is produced based on the same experimentation and software is developed incrementally rather than from scratch.

Taking this logic one step further by facilitating reuse across communities, although more challenging, would favour interdisciplinarity and mutualising the significant intellectual and technical investments underlying the data analysis, thereby allowing it to scale. The compute and data continuum should favour the reuse of software in the Exabyte era. Technically, this can be achieved through libraries, software repositories, and matching software to functional needs of the projects. One can also generate wrappers for existing software from another language using an API. In terms of policy, beyond the production of software for a given purpose, projects should be encouraged to produce or contribute to libraries in order to both increase reusability and harmonize the software stack. This will in turn, facilitate development and efficiency on one hand, as well as improve deployment aided by libraries which are optimised for the platform and compute intensive tasks and I/O on the other hand.

3.2 Environmental sustainability

This section addresses environmental sustainability from the user viewpoint: that of the scientists running software on the infrastructure and that of the IT personnel in charge of operations. Neither of these groups has a direct impact on the fabrication and end-of-life phases of the equipment but, as key players in its value chain, can influence upstream and downstream phases based on how they procure and dispose of it.

Recommendations in this section include but extend beyond improving the energy efficiency of the systems as, in the past, such improvements have never led to a lasting reduction of impacts. Cheaper, easier access to the resources leads to an increase of demand (when it is highly priced and elastic) such that overall the increased usage outweighs the gain resulting from the improvements²⁵. On this point, it is important to note that increased energy usage is not inherently negative. It can be considered acceptable, or even desirable, if the benefits outweigh the negative environmental impacts. This ought to be the result of a trade-off implying quantifying direct and indirect environmental impacts and social benefits.

Although the focus is often on energy, largely for cost or procurement reasons, we consider that sustainability decision-making should rely on Life-Cycle Assessments (LCA) and encompass all 16 impact categories, as defined in the Product Environmental Footprint method recommended by the European

²⁵ This is known as the rebound effect or Jevons' paradox.

Commission (see [Table 2](#)), in order to avoid transfers between phases or across impacts, and allow for systemic reasoning.

Table 2: Environmental impact categories as defined in the Product Environmental Footprint method recommended by the European Commission.

Impact category / Indicator	Unit	Description
Climate change – total, fossil, biogenic and land use	kg CO ₂ -eq	Indicator of potential global warming due to emissions of greenhouse gases into the air. Divided into 3 subcategories based on the emission source: (1) fossil resources, (2) bio-based resources and (3) land use change.
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11-eq	Indicator of emissions to air that causes the destruction of the stratospheric ozone layer.
Acidification	kg mol H+	Indicator of the potential acidification of soils and water due to the release of gases such as nitrogen oxides and sulphur oxides
Eutrophication – freshwater	kg PO ₄ -eq	indicator of the enrichment of the freshwater ecosystem with nutritional elements, due to the emission of nitrogen or phosphor-containing compounds
Eutrophication – marine	Kg N-eq	Indicator of the enrichment of the marine ecosystem with nutritional elements, due to the emission of nitrogen-containing compounds.
Eutrophication – terrestrial	mol N-eq	Indicator of the enrichment of the terrestrial ecosystem with nutritional elements, due to the emission of nitrogen-containing compounds.
Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC-eq	Indicators of emissions of gases that affect the creation of photochemical ozone in the lower atmosphere (smog) catalysed by sunlight.
Depletion of abiotic resources – minerals and metals	kg Sb-eq	Indicator of the depletion of natural non-fossil resources.
Depletion of abiotic resources – fossil fuels	MJ, net calorific value	Indicator of the depletion of natural fossil fuel resources.
Human toxicity – cancer	CTUh	Impact on humans of toxic substances emitted to the environment. Cancer-related toxic substances.
Human toxicity – non-cancer	CTUh	Impact on humans of toxic substances emitted to the environment. Non-cancer-related toxic substances.
Eco-toxicity (freshwater)	CTUe	Impact on freshwater organisms of toxic substances emitted to the environment.
Water use	m ³ world eq. deprived	Indicator of the relative amount of water used, based on regionalized water scarcity factors.
Land use	Dimensionless	Measure of the changes in soil quality (Biotic production, Erosion resistance, Mechanical filtration).

Ionising radiation, human health	kBq U-235	Damage to human health and ecosystems linked to the emissions of radionuclides.
Particulate matter emissions	Disease incidence	Indicator of the potential incidence of disease due to particulate matter emissions

Lifecycle assessment for IT equipment in Europe shows that, as a result mainly of its lifetime and the existing energy mix, the impacts of the fabrication phase outweigh those related to usage. Replacing hardware to benefit from efficiency improvements is never energetically beneficial in such conditions²⁶. Additionally, this does not account for other impacts, like acidification, eutrophication, depletion of abiotic resources, human and eco-toxicity which are mostly related to the materials used. Hence a top-level priority which flows down to the recommendations below is to use the hardware for as long as possible.

The power behaviours of IT devices are complex and highly non linear: fixed costs related to the power supply, standby²⁷ and leakage²⁸ powers are significant and CPU cores, for instance, are far from independent power-wise and their behaviour history-dependent. Modelling this is still largely a research topic but it is acknowledged that the most power-effective use of nodes is achieved when the load is high. While this can impede absolute job performance because of resource saturation, concentrating jobs on a minimum number of resources, up to a certain point, allows first for fabricating fewer and then for more effective power management.

Observing use and analysing inputs from SPECTRUMCoP interviews with providers reveal that users and providers share a growth-oriented vision. This is expected in the scientific and high-performance computing contexts where competition is fierce and much progress has recently been achieved through the increase of resources (larger scientific instruments, scaling of computing infrastructures). However, some interviews mention a desire for harmonising and rationalising uses.

²⁶ Proof: let "a" be the energy for fabrications (assumed equal) and "b1, b2" the energy per unit of time for use before and after replacing the hardware, "t1, t2" the durations of use. Replacing the hardware is beneficial if $a + b1 \cdot (t1 + t2) > 2a + b1 \cdot t1 + b2 \cdot t2$ which simplifies to $b1 \cdot t2 > a + b2 \cdot t2$. Then even with $b2 = 0$ we would need $b1 \cdot t2 > a$ while, as fabrication dominates use, we have $a > b1 \cdot (t1 + t2)$.

²⁷ Related to maintaining components at the Vdd potential.

²⁸ Related to the reverse bias current in transistors.

4. Technical activities and recommended actions

The development of a European Compute and Data Continuum presents a series of interdependent technical challenges. A key requirement is the establishment of standardized interfaces that facilitate interoperability between diverse systems and enable efficient use of advanced architectures, such as GPUs, without necessitating extensive custom integration at each computing center. Equally important is the development of robust data pipelines capable of managing massive throughput while adapting to the dynamic resource availability typical of HPC environments. Evolving workflows, particularly those incorporating machine learning, offer opportunities for accelerated scientific discovery but also necessitate significant efforts in code reengineering, performance optimization, and advanced scheduling. Additionally, strict security and authorization requirements at HPC facilities must be addressed in a manner that maintains data integrity and aligns with the WLCG Trust model. All this is supported by the Strategy for HPC integration in WLCG/HEP white paper²⁹ from March 2025.

Similarly, the next generation large RA projects LOFAR2.0 and theSKAO are facing the challenges associated with processing significant quantities of data across heterogeneous HPC architectures. In the case of the SKAO, the final data processing steps and the interface with the international scientific community will be in the form of distributed nodes of an SRCNet. Currently smaller in scale than the WLCG, the operations model of SRCNet is similar in that countries, or institutes contribute in-kind resources to run their local nodes. Many of the same requirements and hurdles to be overcome by WLCG and HEP are common to LOFAR2.0 and SRCNet. The following sections examine these challenges in greater detail, proposing strategies for achieving a high-performance, efficient, and secure integration of HPC resources into the HEP computing ecosystem.

4.1 Standardization of Interfaces

Related Capabilities	Resource Federation, Monitoring & Observability, Security & Trust, Orchestration & Workflows, Software Distribution & Execution, Compute Resources, Data Resources, AI/ML and HPC Applications
Related Requirements	2, 4, 5, 6, 15

As established in section 2, today, each supercomputing site uses its own portals, schedulers and software stacks. Therefore, an experiment wishing to run on multiple HPC centers must custom-adapt to each.

HPC centers operate with distinct access protocols, policies, and resource management systems, reflecting their diverse operational requirements. While this heterogeneity serves the needs of individual centers, it poses significant obstacles to integrating these resources into distributed infrastructures such as WLCG and SRCNet. Researchers must manually adapt their workflows to each site's unique requirements, a process that is inefficient, error-prone, and, in some cases, infeasible. Without a standardized approach, scaling the number of participating HPC sites remains a labor-intensive challenge. A concerted effort involving funding agencies, WLCG, SRCNet, HPC organizations, and resource providers is required to define and implement a minimum set of standard interfaces. Collaboration with initiatives such as the EuroHPC JU provide promising avenues for achieving this goal.

It would be highly beneficial for the HEP and RA communities to adopt or develop middleware that presents interoperable interfaces. In addition, collaboration with EuroHPC's Federation Platform (EFP) to adapt its interfaces would simplify the process: the EFP is defining a federated identity and allocation API (with single-sign-on and certificate flows). Aligning with such efforts means WLCG and SKAO users could obtain access tokens usable across all participating systems. For RA, the SKA Regional Centres (SRCNet) can benefit strongly from the integration with these standards so that LOFAR2.0/SKA pipelines can run on any compliant HPC.

²⁹Maria Girone et. al., Strategy for HPC Integration in WLCG/HEP, [10.5281/zenodo.15032798](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15032798)

The increasing diversity of user groups, including those unfamiliar with classical supercomputing or accustomed to different tools and paradigms, with artificial intelligence being a prime example, highlights the need for more diverse and more accessible interfaces.

The EFP architecture emphasizes modularity, flexibility, and API-centricity as core design principles while being minimally intrusive to existing systems. The platform consists primarily of open source components that are integrated to provide necessary connections to federated systems. Examples of key components which are aligned with HEP/RA needs include EFP Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) leveraging MyAccessID, EFP Software Catalogue implementing EasyBuild and EESSI via CernVM-FS for consistent software distribution across systems.

In summary, computing centers currently expose a variety of site-specific interfaces (portals, schedulers, credentials) that complicate integration with distributed infrastructures (WLCG, SRCNet) and require experiments to adapt their workflows to each site. This fragmentation is inefficient and limits scalability. Key findings include the need for a common middleware or API layer and federated authentication/allocation mechanisms.

- **Action:** Develop or adopt standardized interfaces for HPC access, common across all European compute sites. Uniform interfaces would benefit HEP and RA communities and HPC centers through reduced integration effort.
- **Action:** Integrate EuroHPC AAI and allocation APIs into site authentication and scheduling. This means that HPC centers should connect their local account and scheduling systems to EuroHPC federation services so that users can authenticate once via their institutional or VO credentials and their project allocations are automatically recognized and enforced across sites.

4.2 Co-Design of Computing, Data, and Networking Infrastructure

Related Capabilities	Compute Resources, Data Resources
Related Requirements	6, 7, 12, 13

The successful deployment of compute and data continuum capabilities for HEP and RA requires careful co-design of computing, data management, and networking infrastructure to ensure optimal performance and cost-effectiveness. This co-design approach must consider the specific characteristics of scientific workloads, data access patterns, and collaboration requirements that distinguish these domains from commercial and other scientific computing applications.

HPC systems are typically procured based on performance metrics and benchmarks and the needs of established computational disciplines, including lattice quantum chromodynamics (QCD), computational chemistry, astrophysics, and climate modeling. However, the architectural choices often made to support these workloads, such as limited RAM, minimal or absent local storage, restricted IP networking, and highly controlled external connectivity, can render certain HPC systems impractical for HEP workflows. In some cases, technical workarounds can enable partial integration, but these solutions are site-specific, require substantial R&D, decrease workflow efficiency, and introduce significant maintenance burdens. To ensure long-term compatibility, HEP and RA must engage with funding agencies during the design and procurement phases of HPC systems. HPC design and procurement processes must directly incorporate stakeholders from key user communities such as HEP and RA. The most effective way to be part of the co-design process in Europe would be to obtain a recognized status within EuroHPC. In the long term, the HEP and RA communities should seek Strategic Access to EuroHPC resources. On top of guaranteeing a stable share of the resources, it would enable the domains to be part of the design and requirement definition for new HPC systems.

Network infrastructure represents a critical constraint for exascale scientific computing, as the ability to move data efficiently between storage and computing resources often determines overall system performance. The integration of dedicated research networks, commercial cloud connectivity, and

specialized links between major facilities requires careful optimization to support diverse traffic patterns while maintaining security and cost-effectiveness. On this topic, GÉANT has been awarded a contract by the [EuroHPC JU](#) to deliver high-capacity, secure, pan-European connectivity for Europe’s supercomputing infrastructure. This hyperconnected network aims to connect selected HPC centres, national supercomputers, AI factories, quantum facilities, and research and data centres across the continent, enabling seamless collaboration for researchers, industry, and the public sector. The project covers the design, implementation, and operation of the hyperconnectivity infrastructure over a period of 48 months

In summary, most current European HPC systems are optimized for other scientific domains and often have limited memory, ephemeral storage, and restricted I/O, features that hinder HEP/RA workloads. Key findings emphasize that HEP/RA communities must influence system design, become recognized stakeholders in EuroHPC and national procurement, and embed their requirements early. For instance, the Destination Earth climate initiative secured multi-year exascale access via strategic EuroHPC support demonstrating how strategic partnerships can secure needed resources.

- **Action:** Seek official “strategic access” or long-term allocations in EuroHPC/national HPC programs. This would allow HEP and SKA communities to gain stable compute shares and a voice in new system design.
- **Action:** Fund initiatives on software-defined, programmable networking to enable intelligent, high-performance data movement.

4.3 Software Portability and Heterogeneous Architectures

Related Capabilities	Software Distribution & Execution, Orchestration & Workflows, AI/ML and HPC Applications, Compute Resources
Related Requirements	4, 5, 11

Both HEP and RA rely on extensive and highly specialized codebases that have often been developed over many years by large collaborations. Historically, these applications have been optimized for x86_64 CPU architectures, which dominated WLCG computing resources. In contrast, modern HPC centers increasingly emphasize heterogeneous computing architectures, particularly GPUs, for their superior energy efficiency and computational throughput. Efficient utilization of these accelerators requires substantial modifications to existing software, including parallelization strategies tailored to specific hardware. While portable programming models and libraries have made progress in easing this transition, significant challenges remain. Existing AI/ML workflows are often the first to adopt GPUs due to their naturally parallel nature and reliance on well-supported libraries like TensorFlow or PyTorch. However, general-purpose HEP event simulation, reconstruction, and analysis codes remain largely CPU-bound. Continued reliance on x86_64 CPUs restricts HEP applications to architectures that are no longer advancing as rapidly in terms of performance and energy efficiency. Without addressing portability, HEP risks being unable to leverage cutting-edge HPC resources, limiting scientific output and inflating computing costs.

Modern and legacy applications require access to configuration files and software environments, often distributed through CVMFS for HEP. A comprehensive survey among HEP experiments is needed to assess their readiness for accelerated architectures, evaluate the feasibility of adopting portability frameworks, and identify high-impact pilot projects for heterogeneous computing. Establishing a mechanism for continuously monitoring the evolution of GPU usage and its impact on computing models will be essential for future-proofing HEP software infrastructure.

In summary, HEP/RA software stacks have been developed for HTC workflows using CPU-only platforms, but modern HPC emphasizes accelerators (GPUs, AI chips). A key finding is that, without adaptation, HEP/RA will under-utilize future resources. Portable programming models and containerization are critical to decouple code from hardware. Experiments must identify which applications (simulation, reconstruction, etc.) can exploit accelerators and refactor them accordingly.

- **Action:** Fund surveys of experiment codebases for accelerator and HPC readiness and identify priority applications for modernization.
- **Action:** Fund pilot projects to port critical codes using portability frameworks and optimize HPC exploitation. Produce optimized prototypes and best practices.
- **Action:** Use CVMFS and/or containers to encapsulate complex software for distribution. This includes GPU-enabled ML frameworks (TensorFlow, PyTorch) and related libraries to ensure AI-driven workflows run efficiently on both grid and supercomputers.
- **Action:** Support curation of software and associated documentation (metadata , repos etc) following open science policies and FAIR best practices.

4.4 Data Management and Network Performance

Related Capabilities	Data Resources, AI/ML and HPC Applications
Related Requirements	6, 7, 8, 9, 12

Efficient data access is critical for HEP and RA applications running on HPC systems, as data handling directly affects the ability to fully utilize computational resources. While experiments have developed advanced data management systems, HPC facilities were not designed for data-intensive workloads, creating challenges that must be addressed to ensure performance at scale.

HPC sites are generally not intended for long-term storage of large datasets, partly due to concerns around data ownership and preservation. Instead, storage is primarily used for transient data or for checkpointing long workflows and therefore large volumes must be transferred in for processing and exported afterward. This model requires temporary storage capacity to scale with compute allocations and deliver sufficient performance. These requirements are shared with workloads like AI applications, which need HPC resources and access to data staged from external data sources.

Another major constraint is network connectivity. Data must be moved in and out of HPC facilities at a rate that matches compute speed, which makes reliable, high-throughput networking essential. At minimum, HPC sites need strong connectivity to WLCG centers and SRCNet nodes, which needs to be realized via e.g., the GÉANT Network. However, there are currently no common tools for automating large-scale data transfers between WLCG, SRCNet, and HPC sites (Fenix integration with FTS was achieved only at PoC level³⁰), forcing reliance on solutions offered by individual HPC centers which differ from site to site and which are not optimised for the data transport needs of HEP/RA. This complicates integration and raises concerns about scalability.

The current limitations prevent major uptake of HPC sites in HEP and RA, and only a portion of the available HPC sites in Europe are currently exploited. Future growth in data volumes and processing demands makes it critical to develop standard, open interfaces for data transfer and storage access at HPC sites so as to fully exploit them. Close attention must also be paid to site policies, such as restricted general connectivity from compute nodes, which could further constrain operations.

In summary, HEP/RA workflows handle multi-petabyte datasets, but HPC sites rarely provide long-term archival storage. Their file systems are optimized for short-term high-speed use, so large data volumes must be staged in and out for each campaign. Key findings stress that scalable data integration requires robust, high-bandwidth networks and automated transfer tools.

- **Action:** Conduct combined SRCNet-WLCG-HPC data challenges to validate end-to-end workflows and identify bottlenecks under realistic loads.
- **Action:** Establish a coordinated programme to develop and deploy standard, high-throughput data transfer tools and network integration across WLCG, SRCNet, and HPC sites, interoperable with the EFP. This should include the design of common data movement interfaces, performance tuning over e.g., the GÉANT backbone, and shared deployment of optimized transfer services (e.g. FTS, Rucio, Globus, iRODS) to replace current site-specific solutions.

³⁰ <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2919584/files/document.pdf>

- **Action:** Fund projects to harmonize policies across computing centers to facilitate integration with HEP/RA and other communities' workflow orchestration, and prove interoperability via data challenges.

4.5 Workflow Adaptation and Optimization

Related Capabilities	Orchestration & Workflows, Software Distribution & Execution, Resource Federation, Security & Trust, Monitoring & Observability
Related Requirements	1, 2, 3, 5, 15

HEP experiments rely on complex, diverse workflows to manage tasks such as data processing, reprocessing, Monte Carlo event generation, detector simulation, and physics analysis. The RA workflows are similarly complex. These workflows, developed over decades for HEP and representing significant community investment, are fundamental to interpreting experimental data, simulating particle interactions, and maximizing physics output. Well-established workflow systems handle the majority of these computational needs within HEP, but integration with HPC centers remains limited.

To improve HPC usability for HEP, a more uniform mechanism for integrating experiment workflows with HPC resource management systems is necessary. Given the diversity of tasks, workflows must be adapted to exploit the computational models of HPC environments while preserving their scientific objectives. The IRI project³¹ classifies workflows into several broad categories based on their computational patterns and resource demands. Additionally, the EFP provides a DAG-based workflow engine designed to support complex scheduling and resource orchestration across federated HPC infrastructures. Alternatively the Computing Elements solutions currently exploited by HEP/RA (ARC-CE/HTCondor-CE) could be configured to access HPC systems (this is already done for instance by the ATLAS experiment with EuroHPC Vega³²).

Time-Sensitive Patterns: Time-sensitive workflows require rapid processing and responsiveness, driven by needs such as fast event scouting, rapid re-training and tuning of real-time machine learning models, and data quality monitoring. These tasks depend on immediate data access and low-latency compute cycles, making their execution on HPC centers challenging under current conditions.

Data-Integration-Intensive Patterns: Another class of workflows is characterized by large-scale data integration and processing. These include detector calibration, data reduction, and complex analyses that extract physics results from extensive datasets. Efficient execution of these workflows depends not only on computing power but also on robust data handling and storage capabilities, which are often constrained by HPC policies and architectures.

Long-term Campaign Patterns: Finally, long-term campaign workflows dominate HEP computational demand. These campaigns span years and include event generation, detailed detector simulations, repeated event reconstruction, and derivation of analysis-ready datasets. End-to-end processing, meaning sequentially executing the full chain of workflows, from event generation to final data derivation or analysis, is very important to minimise data flows to and from the HPC. Such tasks require substantial, sustained computing resources and benefit most from platforms that support long-term engagement and continuity. HPC centers that lack policies supporting persistent, multi-year campaigns are a poor match for these workflows.

At present, only a few HEP workflows have been optimized for HPC architectures, data management models, and authorization systems, typically tailored for a single HPC center. Policy constraints, such as the lack of general internet connectivity from compute (worker) nodes, further complicate integration. This limits the ability to run pilot-based workload management systems that rely on dynamic, late scheduling of tasks to resources.

Fully leveraging HPC centers requires the ability to execute a broader range of HEP workflows, particularly those with the highest computational demands. Without this capability, workflow selection becomes more

³¹ IRI Architecture Blueprint <https://doi.org/10.2172/1984466>

³² <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1140/epic/s10052-024-13701-w>

complex and resource utilization suffers. Moving forward, collaboration between experiments and HPC initiatives is essential to identify workflows best suited for HPC execution under current constraints. This includes assessing the impact of technical and policy limitations and developing strategies to mitigate them. Establishing such a consensus will be critical for maximizing the scientific benefit of HPC resources for HEP.

In summary, HEP and RA workflows are complex, multi-stage systems developed over decades to support data simulation, reconstruction, and analysis. However, their integration with HPC centers remains limited due to differing software environments, network policies, and scheduling models. To exploit HPC effectively, workflows must be adapted to these environments and coordinated across experiments and HPC providers.

- **Action:** Integrate existing application specific workflow systems with HPC resource managers to enable native submission, data staging, and monitoring across federated infrastructures to allow for orchestration of complex workflows across grids and supercomputers.

4.6 Security, Authorization, and Authentication

Related Capabilities	Security & Trust, Resource Federation
Related Requirements	2, 3, 5, 9

HEP collaborations rely on the WLCG Trust model, which enables sites to grant access to users and workflows based on their membership in federated Virtual Organizations (VOs). This approach simplifies user management but presents challenges when integrating with HPC centers that impose stricter authentication and authorization policies. Unlike WLCG, most HPC centers do not support VO-based access control, nor do they have federated identity management systems capable of handling dynamic authorization via entitlements. Current practices require individual users to obtain site-specific credentials, limiting workflow automation and increasing administrative overhead. In addition to this, HPC centers privilege, if not require, accounts to be linked to identifiable individuals, and do not encourage the use of service-related accounts.

While tolerable for limited workflows, the absence of a federated model ultimately constrains the efficient use of HPC resources by large collaborations. Addressing this gap requires the development of a security framework that balances the global, distributed nature of HEP with the specific security requirements of HPC centers.

The foundation of such a solution would be a federated Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) based on industry standards. This would enable users to authenticate once and access multiple sites securely, with consistent authorization policies. Building such an infrastructure is essential to facilitate international collaboration, ensure compliance with regulations, and fully integrate HPC resources into the HEP computing ecosystem.

The EFP is starting to fill this gap by enabling MyAccessId and Edugain Access to EuroHPC systems, therefore the current AAI system used by HEP/RA (typically Indigo-IAM) will need to be made interoperable. A notable missing piece in the EFP is the support for service accounts, which is often required by the HEP/RA communities.

In summary, HEP collaborations rely on a VO-based trust model (central VOMS) and X.509 certificates, whereas HPC centers typically require independent accounts or federated identities. Key findings highlight the need for a unified AAI framework: users should authenticate once and have their roles recognized everywhere.

- **Action:** Build a federated AAI that maps VO membership to HPC access control to enable users to sign in once and gain appropriate privileges on all sites, interoperable with the EFP.
- **Action:** invest in translation services which map identities from different AAI infrastructures.
- **Action:** Harmonize HPC center authorization policies to accept federated identities to eliminate the requirement of per-site account management.

- Action:** Develop standardized support for service accounts within the federated AAI framework. HEP/RA communities should work with the EFP, EuroHPC sites, and AAI providers to define a secure, auditable model for service accounts that aligns with both HEP/RA automation needs and HPC security policies.

4.7 AI/ML Integration and Computational Trends

Related Capabilities	AI/ML and HPC Applications, Compute Resources , Data Resources, Software Distribution & Execution
Related Requirements	4, 5, 8, 11, 12, 13

AI and Machine Learning (ML) techniques present significant opportunities for HEP and RA, enabling new approaches to simulation, event selection, reconstruction, and data analysis. These methods can outperform traditional algorithms in both efficiency and scalability, accelerating scientific progress.

The growing role of GPUs in ML applications is particularly relevant, driven by substantial industry investment in AI-optimized hardware. However, this shift presents challenges for HEP. The industry focus on accelerating low-precision computations for AI comes at the expense of double-precision performance, which remains critical for many traditional HEP and RA workflows, but also for other domains. As this trend continues, each experiment will need to assess which computational tasks can be refactored to leverage AI/ML techniques and which will require specialized hardware capable of high-precision calculations.

These challenges highlight the importance of close collaboration between data-intensive scientific communities and HPC system designers. Engaging at the design stage is essential to ensure future computing resources can adequately support both AI-driven workflows and the precision requirements of classical HEP computations.

In summary, AI and Machine Learning are becoming increasingly important tools in HEP/RA (for simulation, reconstruction, analysis). In parallel, HPC hardware is shifting toward AI-optimized, low-precision accelerators. Key findings note that experiments must strategically refactor suitable tasks for ML while planning for high-precision workloads. Close collaboration is needed so that future HPC procurements include both powerful AI accelerators and sufficient double-precision compute.

- Action:** Identify analysis and simulation tasks suitable for ML acceleration and fund and coordinate development of AI-driven workflows.
- Action:** Communicate precision and performance needs to HPC hardware planners to ensure new systems have a balanced hardware mix. This applies not only to HEP/RA but other scientific domains as well (digital twins, traditional simulation).
- Action:** Train physicists and astronomers in ML theory, frameworks and tools to build the capacity to fully exploit AI factories. Cross-domain training is encouraged.

4.8 Long-Term Resource Provisioning and Accounting

Related Capabilities	Monitoring & Observability, Resource Federation
Related Requirements	1, 10, 13

HPC resource allocations are typically awarded through peer-reviewed proposals with usage limited to a fixed period, often one year. This model contrasts with the long-term nature of LHC experiments, which operate over multiple decades with sustained computing demands. The LHC computing model relies on multi-year resource commitments formalized through Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) with WLCG sites, ensuring continuous availability and predictable resource planning aligned with physics goals.

While LHC experiments invest in portable software capable of running across diverse platforms, the lack of long-term allocations at HPC centers limits the return on further adaptation efforts. Multi-year or renewable

annual guaranteed allocations would enable experiments to fully leverage such investments and integrate HPC resources more effectively into their computing models.

Strategic science initiatives, such as DestinE, recognized by the European Commission benefit from stable access to HPC resources without yearly reapplication. HEP aims to strengthen its engagement with EuroHPC and national HPC programs by responding systematically to access opportunities, including development, benchmarking, regular and extreme-scale access, AI, and data-intensive application calls, while building the internal capacity to position itself as a candidate for future strategic access.

In summary, LHC and SKA experiments can span many years, but HPC allocations are typically granted for one year. Key findings stress that multi-year or easily-renewable allocations are essential. HEP/RA should aim to secure long-term commitments and ensure usage is tracked alongside WLCG/SRCNet resources.

- **Action:** Develop multi-year and strategic HPC projects to secure guaranteed compute allocations aimed to create stable capacity aligned with experimental timelines.
- **Action:** Fund a study to propose practical models for multi-year or renewable HPC allocations aligned with experimental lifecycles.

5. Conclusions

The SPECTRUM Technical Blueprint demonstrates that Europe's scientific ambitions in HEP and RA would greatly benefit from a fully integrated compute and data continuum. Such an ecosystem brings together HPC, HTC, cloud, edge, and emerging technologies, but its success will depend on addressing a series of fundamental challenges. This Technical Blueprint has outlined a comprehensive vision for the European Compute and Data Continuum, designed to meet the needs of data-intensive scientific domains such as HEP and RA. It translates community evidence into a modular design that structures the continuum around key capabilities, defining the technical foundations required for Europe to maintain leadership in scientific discovery. Even if targeted to the HEP and RA communities, the expectation is that the findings and recommendations are common to other computing- and data- intensive scientific workflows, especially if globally distributed; the Blueprint, hence, must be considered in more ample terms than those limited to the specific domains.

A number of consistent themes emerged during the creation of the Blueprint and the previous work done in SPECTRUM. A first finding is the need for standardization of interfaces and that federating capabilities and interoperability are indispensable. Today's infrastructures remain fragmented, with each site exposing distinct APIs, protocols, and operational practices. This hinders interoperability, complicates cross-border workflows, and makes reproducibility fragile. Establishing open, community-driven standards for job submission, data access, monitoring, and accounting is therefore essential. Only through common interfaces can the continuum become more than the sum of its parts.

Second, is the co-design of compute and data infrastructures. HEP and RA workflows do not separate computation from data movement, both are tightly coupled, often requiring massive parallel compute and transfers in the same workflow. The continuum must therefore be co-designed with balanced investment in compute, storage, and networking, ensuring that bottlenecks are removed and resources evolve in harmony with scientific requirements. Engagement between scientific collaborations, (Euro)HPC centers, and network providers must become a structured, long-term process. Much work has already been done in the HEP community to integrate HPC resources with experiment workflows both in Europe and in the US^{33 34 35 36 37 38}

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The third challenge concerns software portability across heterogeneous architectures. As Europe invests in diverse hardware such as GPUs, FPGAs, ARM processors and quantum accelerators, scientific codes must be able to run efficiently across all or most of them. Current software stacks are often bound to specific architectures, limiting flexibility and increasing maintenance costs. Investing in portable libraries, containerized environments, and compiler toolchains that target multiple backends is thus a priority. For communities like HEP and RA, where workflows must remain operational for decades and hence generations of computing systems, portability is of utmost importance.

A fourth key finding is the importance of workflow management. Scientific research increasingly depends on complex, multi-step workflows that span facilities and scientific domains. These must be orchestrated seamlessly across the continuum, with robust scheduling, provenance tracking, and error handling. Without such workflow intelligence, the continuum risks remaining fragmented and underutilized.

Security and trust also emerge as essential. Authorization and authentication mechanisms remain uneven across infrastructures, creating barriers to collaboration. A federated approach to identity and access management, building on initiatives like eduGAIN, is needed to ensure that researchers can move seamlessly between resources. Security must be embedded at the architectural level, not retrofitted as an afterthought.

³³ <https://zenodo.org/records/15032799>

³⁴ <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.07376>

³⁵ <https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.14647>

³⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202024509002>

³⁷ <https://doi.org/10.22323/1.378.0003>

³⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202125102042>

³⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202533701107>

The Blueprint also highlights the transformative role of AI/ML integration. Machine learning is no longer peripheral to scientific discovery, it is embedded in many parts of the HEP and RA communities production and analysis workflows. The continuum must therefore provide AI/ML services at scale, including distributed training environments, inference platforms, and model registries. Supporting and providing these capabilities ensures that AI accelerates, rather than complicates, scientific workflows.

Finally, long-term sustainability is a defining concern. Resource provisioning and accounting must move from short-term, project-specific allocations to stable, predictable, multi-year commitments. Transparent accounting mechanisms should span HPC, HTC, cloud, and data infrastructures, enabling tracking usage as well as energy and carbon costs. For HEP and RA, whose scientific lifecycles extend over decades, this long-term perspective is the only way to guarantee reproducibility, scientific continuity, and strategic autonomy.

Taken together, these findings define both the challenges and the opportunities. Europe has the chance to build a continuum that is open, federated, and sustainable. This will require technical innovation in standardization, portability, workflows, and AI integration, but also organizational innovation in governance, funding, and long-term provisioning. If Europe acts now, researchers will soon be able to, for example, transparently combine GPU nodes in France, cloud services in Italy, and edge devices in Spain within a single workflow. Such a future will not only secure the scientific leadership of HEP and RA, but also establish a model digital infrastructure for all data-driven disciplines.

Next steps should focus on piloting and validation. Technically, prototypes and pilots must validate the Blueprint outlined here, ensuring interoperability across domains and readiness for production use. Organizationally, governance and funding models must be agreed upon at European and national levels, embedding long-term commitments that guarantee continuity. Without these steps, the Blueprint will not come into operational reality.

In conclusion, the Compute and Data Continuum is not simply an infrastructure plan but a strategic investment in Europe's scientific future. By integrating technical excellence with policy alignment and sustainability, it provides the foundation for discoveries at the energy and cosmic frontiers, and a model for data-driven science across disciplines.

Appendices

A. The Compute and Data Continuum

The compute and data continuum integrates heterogeneous computational resources, federated data systems, and adaptive orchestration frameworks into an interoperable infrastructure optimized for cross-domain scientific workflows. The architecture enables seamless operation across leadership-class HPC systems, quantum co-processors, and elastic cloud-edge platforms while adhering to FAIR data principles. The following subsections describe the different capabilities.

Figure 1: Capability map for the HEP and RA communities.

A.1 Compute Resources

The Compute Resources capability is the foundational layer of the European Compute and Data Continuum, providing seamless access to heterogeneous computational resources distributed across HPC centers, community and commercial clouds, edge infrastructures, and emerging quantum platforms. For data-intensive domains such as HEP and RA, the Compute Continuum transforms a fragmented ecosystem of sites into a federated, performance-optimized environment that can deliver exascale throughput.

HPC: High-performance computing is set to become a core component for HEP and RA. HEP experiments have been using HPC resources for more than 15 years, with HPC now making significant contributions to

both production and analysis pipelines^{40,41,42,43,44}. For example, the WLCG already comprises approximately 1.4 million cores and over 1.5 EB of storage across 170 sites (home.cern), and HPC resources exploited by experiments range from 3 sites integrated by ALICE and LHCb, to more than 10 sites by ATLAS and CMS. The upcoming High-Luminosity LHC and SKAO will only increase these demands. To integrate HPC into the continuum, standardized interfaces and APIs must be used so that large-scale batch jobs can be submitted, monitored, and managed across federated HPC centers. This involves bridging local batch schedulers (e.g. Slurm) with global workload managers used by experiments, so that simulation and reconstruction tasks can run on HPC without manual effort (as already piloted in HEP). Similar integrations are needed in order to use accelerators such as GPUs transparently, as both CERN and SKA are exploring heterogeneous computing for AI-accelerated analysis (e.g. GPU enabled queues in SLURM can be made available and accessible via middleware such as DIRAC⁴⁵) Importantly, federated identity and accounting layers to allow resource allocations and usage tracking to span multiple HPC sites are also needed (following what has been done already in HTC Federations in WLCG).

At the same time, cloud integration offers a complementary pathway for obtaining additional capacity, although the nature of this elasticity depends strongly on the type of cloud, their configuration, policies and utilization. Public hyperscale clouds aim to provide genuine on-demand, elastic resources due to their large overcapacity and commercial operating model, making them suitable for e.g., bursty or exploratory workloads. In contrast, academic and on-prem research clouds, which typically operate at a smaller scale and are often funded to match expected scientific demand, make it less likely that they always provide immediate, on-demand provisioning. In these environments, cloud interfaces hence mainly offer more operational flexibility rather than guaranteed elasticity: sites may choose to adjust allocations between tenants or VOs, or reserve capacity for specific communities, but overall utilisation patterns often resemble queue-based (HPC-like) scheduling rather than commercial cloud bursting.

Within these constraints, federated cloud stacks (e.g. OpenStack-based infrastructures, the EGI Federated Cloud, or EOSC services) still provide important benefits by exposing a unified mechanism to deploy VMs or containerised environments across participating sites. Suitable scientific workflows can then spin up VMs or Kubernetes pods where needed, for example, cloud bursts for Monte Carlo generation or interactive analysis, and shut them down when done (e.g. [CloudComputingElement](#) from DIRAC). Container registries and orchestration services ensure portability across cloud and HPC. Several European efforts (EGI Federated Cloud, EOSC portals) already demonstrate cloud virtualization for research. For instance, the DataCloud⁴⁶ project showed how big-data pipelines could be deployed across federated cloud sites to stay close to data sources (egi.eu). By pooling cloud resources, experiments can handle bursty workloads without long waits for some categories of workloads (e.g. of smaller scale).

Real-Time & Low-Latency Computing: Many HEP and RA instruments produce data at the “edge”, e.g. detector electronics or telescope antenna arrays, that must be reduced in size before transfer to central facilities. Edge computing nodes, located near or on-site at observatories and colliders, run real-time pipelines for filtering, compression, or transient detection. For example, LOFAR and the SKAO radio telescope arrays generate raw streams on the order of 10–100 Tb/s⁴⁷, which is far too much to send directly offsite, so initial calibration and gridding are done at on-site digital signal processors. By processing data at the source, edge nodes reduce network load and latency. Low-latency analytics (using FPGAs, GPUs or other accelerators) enable rapid responses, for instance immediate follow-up of astrophysical transients. Integrating instrument control systems with edge compute also allows health monitoring of detectors and

⁴⁰Strategy for HPC Integration in WLCG/HEP, Maria Girone et al. (2025) <https://zenodo.org/records/15032799>

⁴¹US ATLAS and US CMS HPC and Cloud Blueprint, Fernando Barreiro Megino et al. (2023) <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.07376>

⁴²Integrating the Perlmutter HPC system in the ALICE Grid, Sergiu Weisz et al. (2025) <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202533701107>

⁴³Integrating LHCb workflows on HPC resources: status and strategies, Federico Stagni et al. (2020) <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202024509002>

⁴⁴ Bard, D., Benjamin, D., Calafiura, P., Childers, T., Fisk, I., Girone, M., Gutsche, O., Hufnagel, D., Klimentov, A., Lancon, E., Martinez Outschoorn, V. I., & Wuerthwein, F. (2025). Strategy For HPC Integration (US) Whitepaper. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17854525>

⁴⁵ https://doc.grid.surfsara.nl/en/latest/Pages/Practices/gpu_jobs.html

⁴⁶ <https://www.egi.eu/case-study/datacloud/>

⁴⁷ <https://www.skao.int/en/explore/big-data>

feedback (e.g. beam diagnostics in accelerators). In summary, edge computing extends the continuum by handling the first stages of massive data flows, ensuring that only valuable information traverses the wide-area network to central archives. This data-reduction at the edge comes at the cost of information loss, but is necessary due to the high data rates. It is simply not feasible to store all raw data.

Quantum Computing: While quantum technologies hold long-term promise, their practical impact on HEP and RA remains limited in the near term. Current exploration is largely experimental, focusing on specific proof-of-concept studies in optimization or simulation. Within the compute continuum, quantum integration is therefore treated as a future-oriented interoperability layer rather than a core operational component. Its role is to ensure that emerging quantum or hybrid quantum-classical workflows can be connected to existing infrastructures when relevant, without disrupting established pipelines. The emphasis for now remains on readiness and modular integration, rather than active deployment.

Together, the HPC, cloud, and edge components make the computing infrastructure seamless, scalable and flexible, allowing HEP and RA users to run tightly-coupled simulations, large-scale data analyses, and modern AI/ML workloads across the continuum with minimal friction.

A.2 Data Resources

Scientific data in HEP and RA are massive, distributed and federated. The Data Continuum is a federated infrastructure that enables scientific data to be stored, moved, discovered, and preserved across geographically distributed and technologically heterogeneous sites. For data-intensive disciplines such as HEP and RA, where exabyte-scale datasets are generated and shared globally, the Data Fabric is not a peripheral service but a central enabler of scientific discovery. It transforms fragmented storage silos into a seamless, policy-compliant, and performance-optimized ecosystem.

Federated Storage:

The continuum relies on a distributed storage capability spanning many sites, which together present a unified namespace to users and applications. Experiments such as ATLAS and CMS now manage more than an exabyte of data across over 120 storage centers using systems like Rucio. A critical aspect of this capability is data replication and integrity management. Replication rules ensure that each dataset is stored at multiple geographically distinct sites, balancing performance, resilience, and cost. Integrity checks, based on checksums or cryptographic hashes, are performed during transfers and periodically verified in storage to detect corruption or loss. Automated repair mechanisms can re-replicate damaged or missing files from verified copies elsewhere in the federation, maintaining long-term data reliability. Furthermore, access controls and accounting mechanisms are embedded at the storage level to enforce data governance and monitor resource usage across the federation. In practice, HEP and RA communities already share similar approaches: for example, the ESCAPE project demonstrated the applicability of Rucio for managing distributed data from the SKA, CTA, and Rubin Observatory (rucio.cern.ch/community). Within the continuum, this federated storage capability presents a coherent, policy-driven view of data—users simply request a dataset, and the system locates and retrieves it seamlessly, regardless of where the bytes physically reside.

Data Transfer: For both HEP and RA, data movement at scale is as critical as compute cycles. Moving multi-petabyte datasets between facilities requires high-performance data movement services and a performant underpinning network. Dedicated transfer nodes and optimized protocols (e.g. GridFTP, Globus, XRootD, FTS) are used to shuttle data reliably. The transfer layer orchestrates transfers, it schedules bulk copies to avoid saturating links and queues, and automatically retries failed transfers. For example, LHC experiments regularly transfer tens of petabytes per day between CERN and remote Tier-1 centers, coordinating thousands of files in flight. Together with dedicated research network backbones such as GÉANT, LHCOPN, and LHCONE, the high-performance fiber infrastructure ensures that raw and processed data flow efficiently across the continuum.

Data Discovery and Cataloging: A critical need is for scientists to find and understand data. The continuum needs to include metadata catalogs and registries to make data (incl. software) findable. Each dataset is tagged with rich, standardized metadata (experiment, date, conditions, format, analysis provenance, etc.). Global catalog services keep track of all registered datasets and their physical locations. For example, Rucio

provides lookup services and has been used in HEP for years while RA is starting to adopt it. RA also has its own services such as, e.g., the distributed LOFAR long-term archive that provides rich metadata, look-up and more. Provenance tracking is integrated: as data move and transform, metadata records the lineage (which original files were processed by which code version to produce current datasets). This supports the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles increasingly mandated in research.

Data Lifecycle Management: Scientific datasets have long lifespans and varying usage patterns. The continuum enforces lifecycle policies. For example, raw data might be retained for a fixed period, intermediate formats deleted sooner, and analysis-ready data preserved indefinitely. Automated policies may move data between storage tiers based on access frequency and cost. Quality assurance monitors periodically verify data integrity (checksums, error rates) and rebuild lost fragments if needed. An example in HEP is the ATLAS Data Carousel project⁴⁸. For archival preservation, the system includes curation metadata such as data format, documentation, and software environment, to ensure future usability. In the HEP context, these policies are encoded in Rucio rules that replicate datasets N times and expire older replicas when space is needed. RA projects similarly define retention for different data products (e.g. calibrated images vs. raw voltages). Thus, the lifecycle block ensures that valuable data remain accessible and trustworthy over decades, while minimizing costs and respecting any legal or safety requirements.

A.3 Software Distribution and Execution

The software, compiler, and library ecosystem is the critical abstraction layer that bridges scientific applications with the heterogeneous resources of the Compute and Data Continuum. While the Compute and Data resources provide the raw infrastructure, it is the software stack that makes these resources usable, and enables portable, and reproducible workflows for global collaborations. For communities such as HEP and RA, whose workflows must run consistently across hundreds of sites and over decades, a robust and harmonized software and execution environment is indispensable.

A central feature of the continuum is the ability to distribute scientific software consistently across federated sites. This is achieved through mechanisms such as software registries, container registries, and virtual file systems.

- **Software and compiler registries** act as catalogues of validated applications, frameworks, and libraries, annotated with metadata on authorship, licensing, and hardware compatibility.
- **Container registries** store portable images (e.g., Docker, Apptainer/Singularity), allowing scientists to encapsulate complex environments and run them reproducibly across HPC, cloud, and edge.
- **Virtual file systems** such as CVMFS enable lightweight, versioned, and up to date distribution of software environments to thousands of nodes, a model already proven in WLCG. CVMFS uses the pull rather than push model of software distribution. Meaning that each client *pulls* (requests/downloads) only the pieces of software it needs, when it needs them.

Together, these services ensure that researchers can access the correct software stack regardless of the underlying hardware or site-specific configuration.

To ensure flexibility, the continuum supports dynamic runtime configuration across heterogeneous systems. This includes, environment module systems for selecting and switching software stacks, automated dependency resolution to prevent conflicts, cross-architecture support for x86, ARM, RISC-V, GPU nodes, and emerging accelerators. Although environment modules are a de facto standard in HPC, they are not yet widely adopted in HEP/RA communities, which rely more heavily on container-based workflows. Within the European HPC ecosystem, EasyBuild has emerged as the de facto standard for module generation, with EESSI, distributed via CVMFS and mandated for EuroHPC systems through the EFP, providing an optimised software compilation and distribution layer. Strengthening alignment between HEP/RA software practices and these EuroHPC approaches represents a concrete, actionable step toward improving interoperability and reducing duplication across the continuum.

The execution environment must also support runtime flexibility, enabling users and workflow systems to request specific software stacks, compilers, or libraries declaratively. This includes selecting between different MPI implementations, choosing accelerator-enabled maths libraries, or loading

⁴⁸ Updates to the ATLAS Data Carousel Project, Mikhail Borodin et al. EPJ Web of Conferences 295, 01054 (2024) <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202429501054>

architecture–appropriate builds of AI frameworks such as PyTorch (CUDA), TensorFlow (ROCm), or JAX (XLA). Exposing these capabilities through stable APIs is essential for seamless integration with workflow orchestrators, particularly for applications with strict performance requirements or accelerator dependencies.

For both HEP and RA, portable execution environments ensure that complex reconstruction frameworks, AI/ML models, and simulation codes can run on globally distributed resources with identical behavior. CVMFS, containerization, and workflow provenance already play a central role in the LHC software ecosystem, and is expected to be used in production by more and more scientific initiatives in a short time scale⁴⁹.

A.4 Orchestration and Workflows

The European Compute and Data Continuum will span multiple facilities, resource types, and governance domains. To unlock its potential, scientific workflows must be orchestrated seamlessly across HPC, cloud, edge, and specialized instruments. This requires more than ad-hoc job scheduling and calls for an integrated orchestration layer that manages resources, tasks, and data flows coherently, while ensuring reproducibility and policy compliance. For both HEP and RA, which rely on large, distributed, multi-decade collaborations, orchestration is what transforms a federation of resources into a functioning continuum.

Modern scientific workflows increasingly include AI/ML components for pattern recognition, anomaly detection, and surrogate modeling. The orchestration layer must therefore support the full AI/ML lifecycle, including distributed training across HPC/Cloud, federated learning where data cannot leave sites, inference deployment at the edge for low-latency decisions, and model versioning for reproducibility. In both HEP and RA, this could mean deploying pre-trained models at instrument edges to filter events in real time. In HEP, it could also enable large-scale distributed training of generative models or event reconstruction models on exascale resources.

Workflow Management: Researchers describe analyses as workflows of tasks (data read, calibration, simulation, analysis) with dependencies. A workflow management system captures this DAG of tasks and manages execution end-to-end. These systems also provide resilience, if a job fails at one site, it is retried or moved elsewhere. **Provenance** metadata is recorded automatically for each step, ensuring reproducibility. For example, a HEP experiment could describe an end-to-end simulation chain from event generation through detector simulation to final analysis. The workflow engine then schedules each stage on appropriate resources (HPC, Cloud, CPU, GPU etc.), and records all details in a database. Software portability should ensure that the same workflow can be deployed on a HPC center, a community cloud, or an edge device at a telescope without re-engineering. Emerging standards such as CWL (Common Workflow Language) or WDL (Workflow Description Language) provide promising baselines, but must be extended to support federated, heterogeneous execution environments. Within workflows, **task scheduling** ensures tasks are scheduled efficiently, respecting hardware requirements, data locality, and deadlines. For example, a GPU-intensive training job in HEP should preferentially be dispatched to accelerator-enabled nodes, while a transient detection task in RA must run on edge resources within milliseconds of data capture.

Resource Orchestration: Beyond describing workflows, orchestration dynamically allocates compute, storage, and network resources across facilities. This involves mechanisms for dynamic scaling, e.g., expanding into cloud resources when HPC queues are full, and load balancing, sending tasks to underutilized sites to maximize throughput. Examples are Nextflow, Snakemake, Airflow, Galaxy, etc. For RA in particular, orchestrators must integrate with real-time data streams from telescopes, scheduling compute tasks close to the edge when latency is critical, while offloading heavier processing to HPC or cloud resources.

A.5 AI/ML and HPC Applications

AI/ML and traditional HPC/HTC applications together form the scientific and computational backbone of modern data-intensive research. They drive new methods in simulation, reconstruction, calibration, analysis, and instrument operations, while simultaneously pushing the technological evolution of the continuum. Both

⁴⁹ LOFAR, for example, already deploys its software using CVMFS.

classes of workloads benefit from access to large-scale compute, distributed data fabrics, and interoperable software environments, but they expose different performance characteristics that must be supported in parallel. Ensuring that these heterogeneous workloads can operate efficiently across HPC, HTC, cloud, and data-lake infrastructures is therefore a central requirement of the continuum.

Advanced Analytics and Interactive Exploration: Researchers need tools to explore and analyze large datasets. The continuum offers platforms such as Jupyter notebooks, RStudio, or custom portals linked to the data federation, allowing researchers to query and visualize large datasets through notebooks, dashboards, and statistical tools, bridging traditional batch workflows with real-time exploration. These interactive environments run in the cloud or on HPC visualization nodes, giving scientists graphical and scripting access to data. Statistical and visual analytics libraries (Python, R, machine learning toolkits) are preinstalled. This lowers the barrier for hypothesis generation. Large scale data analysis can start as an interactive process, used to test ideas and solutions on a small-to-medium scale, but can then process as an offline workflow, particularly in cases where the input datasets are PB scale. A seamless transition between the two regimes should be possible, for example via the scale-out of interactive processes from the processing on the user's private machine to large external resources, via tools like Dask.

AI/ML Platforms, Distributed Model Training and Hyperparameter Optimization: AI and ML are becoming indispensable in modern scientific discovery. The continuum provides AI/ML platforms tailored for large-scale, distributed research. Training infrastructure makes available distributed, GPU-rich training environments spanning HPC, cloud, and edge resources thus enabling models to be trained on massive datasets, including exabyte-scale HEP events or petabyte-scale RA visibility data. Scalable inference services enable deployment of trained models, e.g., at the LHC trigger level to classify collision events, or at telescope edges to detect astrophysical transients within milliseconds. Model registries and versioning play a crucial role. Both AI/ML and HPC workflows benefit from robust software, model, and dataset registries. FAIR-compliant repositories facilitate reproducibility, attribution, and long-term preservation and support collaborative development across geographically distributed communities. For example, an astrophysicist can browse a model zoo for a neural network that classifies radio transients and fine-tune it with local data. Federated learning tools provide privacy-preserving approaches that allow AI models to be collaboratively trained across distributed data without moving sensitive or bandwidth-heavy datasets, an approach particularly relevant for geographically dispersed observatories.

Simulation Frameworks and Digital Twins: Many scientific domains require physics simulations. The continuum hosts domain-specific simulation frameworks (e.g. GEANT4 for particle detectors, N-body or fluid solvers for astrophysics). An emerging class of applications builds on digital twins, which combine physics models, operational data, and AI-assisted prediction to represent instruments or detectors in near real time. Digital twin platforms, such as [itwinai](#), allow domain experts to exploit advanced optimisation or multi-node training methods without extensive ML engineering. For RA, digital twins of telescope arrays can for example anticipate calibration drifts or hardware failures while for HEP, digital twins of detectors could for instance model radiation damage or alignment shifts.

Large-Scale Data Processing and Scientific Pipelines: Many HEP and RA applications rely on large-scale, domain-specific processing pipelines that transform raw instrument output into calibrated, analysis-ready data. These include full reconstruction chains, detector calibration workflows, Monte Carlo production, data reduction for RA, and large-scale physics or astrophysics analyses. These pipelines often process petabyte-scale datasets, require sustained compute allocations, and combine CPU- and accelerator-intensive components. Within the continuum, these pipelines must run efficiently on heterogeneous resources and access data through federated mechanisms without requiring per-site customisation. Containerised software environments, standardised data access protocols, and compatibility with heterogeneous architectures are essential to ensuring that these large-scale applications can utilise HPC, HTC, and cloud resources as part of an integrated ecosystem.

A.6 Resource Federation

A European Compute and Data Continuum must allow resources from different providers and domains to function as part of a single, coherent ecosystem. For HEP and RA, where workflows routinely span multiple facilities, this means going beyond isolated access models to enable true **federation of access and**

allocation of continuum resources. Researchers should be able to use HPC, cloud, storage, and edge resources through a unified entry point, with allocations that can be honoured seamlessly across institutional and national boundaries.

At the technical level, this requires **interoperable standards** for job submission, data access, and monitoring, as well as the integration of federated identity and access management systems. Building on existing models such as eduGAIN and the WLCG's Virtual Organisations, the continuum should provide single sign-on across facilities, with support for role-based access, attribute aggregation, and support for service accounts. These mechanisms are essential for ensuring both ease of use and robust security in a federated environment.

Transparent **accounting** is equally important. Usage data, such as CPU/GPU hours, storage consumption, and data transfer volumes, must be collected and reported in a consistent way across all sites. This not only supports fair allocation and equitable participation but also enables funding bodies and infrastructure providers to verify contributions and assess impact. For researchers, transparent accounting builds confidence that resources are distributed fairly, while for policymakers, it provides the accountability needed to sustain investment.

For HEP, this would ensure that exabyte-scale workloads are distributed efficiently across a federation of Tier-0, Tier-1, and Tier-2 centers, with harmonised allocation and usage reporting. For RA, it would allow data from telescopes to flow into i.a., European HPC and HTC facilities in a controlled and federated manner, providing astronomers with seamless access to the resources they need for continuous, multi-decade observations.

A.7 Monitoring and Observability

To operate a complex continuum, comprehensive monitoring and analytics are needed. The Monitoring and Observability block ensures that the European Compute and Data Continuum is not only performant and reliable, but also transparent, efficient, and environmentally responsible. For High Energy Physics (HEP) and Radio Astronomy (RA), which operate on multi-decadal timelines and exascale-scale infrastructures, observability and sustainability are not optional features but foundational requirements.

Infrastructure Monitoring: Observability begins with end-to-end monitoring of the health and performance of resources across the continuum. Compute nodes report CPU/GPU utilization, memory and I/O rates while storage arrays report usage and errors. Data center environmental sensors measure temperature, power consumption, and Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE). A centralized telemetry system ingests these metrics in real time. Automated rules detect outliers (e.g. a failed disk, a supercomputer node overheating) so that maintainers can intervene before failure. For example, many HPC sites already use tools like Prometheus and Grafana to visualize cluster health. Over time, trends and predictive analytics will inform capacity planning (e.g. forecasting that a cluster will be full by next year or that network upgrades are needed). On top of raw infrastructure, **application-level performance monitoring** traces scientific workflows. Each step of a pipeline emits logs and metrics such as job durations, queue wait times, I/O patterns, error counts, etc. Performance monitoring also supports billing and reporting (showing how many core-hours an experiment used). Collectively, these observability data help developers tune code for the continuum and reassure funding agencies that resources are used efficiently.

Operational Intelligence: Raw monitoring data are transformed into actionable intelligence. Analytics and anomaly detection automatically flag unusual behavior, from failing disks to network congestion. Trend analysis and forecasting enable capacity planning, ensuring that infrastructure keeps pace with growing data and compute demands. AI-driven predictive maintenance reduces downtime by identifying hardware likely to fail before it does, a critical feature for 24/7 operations like telescopes or LHC detectors.

Energy Monitoring: Sustainability requires fine-grained measurement and active optimization of energy consumption. Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE), Carbon Usage Effectiveness (CUE) and water utilization are tracked across sites, providing benchmarks for efficiency. The continuum's scheduling system can use this data for "green scheduling", deferring non-urgent jobs to times when renewable energy is available or to more efficient datacenters. Carbon footprint metrics are calculated for accounting and reporting.

This capability could support energy-aware job scheduling in WLCG, real-time monitoring of data-intensive workflows, and predictive maintenance of accelerator computing clusters. It could also provide transparency for EC and member states on the carbon footprint of LHC computing.

A.8 Security and Trust

The European Compute and Data Continuum will be a federated infrastructure spanning multiple countries, institutions, and administrative domains. In such an environment, trust and security are not add-ons but foundational enablers ([AARC Blueprint Architecture](#)). They ensure that (sensitive) data, compute resources, and workflows are protected while still enabling frictionless collaboration across organizational and national boundaries. Both HEP and RA rely heavily on global collaboration, but they have to comply with EU regulations on privacy, data protection, and cybersecurity.

Identity and Access Management (IAM): Access to resources is governed by a federated IAM system. HEP and RA communities rely on global identity federations (such as eduGAIN) so that researchers can use their home institution credentials across all sites. Once authenticated, user attributes (collaboration membership, VO roles, project grants) travel with the identity so that access policies can make decisions. For example, an authenticated physicist's request for a dataset triggers a check in the federated IAM: if he/she is a member of the owning experiment, access is granted. According to a survey carried out by SPECTRUM there is a lot of fragmentation in the currently used tools, almost equally shared between Indigo-IAM, CERN-SSO and EGI Check-in (with MyAccessID being used by the EFP).

Policy Enforcement: Trust in a federated environment depends on shared rules, policies, and validation processes. The trust framework must define the criteria for participation (technical, organizational, and policy compliance) and provide mechanisms for continuous validation of participants. For example, sites must demonstrate that their infrastructure complies with minimum security baselines, privacy regulations, and FAIR principles. Digital certificates and accredited attribute providers reduce reliance on manual validation, making trust decisions scalable (however many modern legal interpretations require that all actions must be traceable to a unique and natural person and this needs to be solved for bulk workloads). In practice, this mirrors existing trust models in the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid but extends them to include HPC and cloud facilities with different compliance regimes. Once policies are defined, they must be enforceable in real time. Policies define rules such as "data from telescope X can only be stored in GDPR-compliant facilities within the EU" or "users must re-authenticate with multi-factor authentication when accessing Tier-0 resources."

Privacy and Data Protection: While most HEP and RA data are not personal, the continuum will inevitably process some sensitive datasets (e.g., medical imaging in cross-domain digital twin applications, AI models trained on personal mobility data for environmental research). Compliance with GDPR and future EU data protection legislation is mandatory. Technical safeguards include encryption at rest and in transit, differential privacy techniques for sensitive AI/ML use cases, federated training of AI models, and logged trails for data access. The framework must also respect data sovereignty, ensuring that data remains within designated jurisdictions when required.

B. Related Initiatives

JENA (Joint ECFA–NuPECC–APPEC) Activities brings together the particle, nuclear, and astroparticle physics communities to coordinate cross-domain challenges. Its working groups have highlighted shared needs in areas such as simulation frameworks, detector software, and data analysis platforms. JENA has been particularly active in promoting sustainable software practices, including the adoption of common development standards and training curricula for research software engineers. The initiative also stresses the importance of long-term funding for software and infrastructure, recognising that major scientific programmes can span decades. JENA’s focus on human resources, through career pathways and skills development, echoes needs expressed by the SPECTRUM Community of Practice.

InPex (International Post-Exascale Project) is an international collaboration among HPC researchers from Europe, the United States, and Japan. It serves as a forum for discussing challenges and opportunities in the exascale and post-exascale era. Topics include hardware–software co-design, HPC–AI–Quantum convergence, the creation of open machine learning models and datasets, FAIR data stewardship, energy efficiency, and ethical considerations around AI. InPex produces reference documents that inform investment strategies and encourage harmonisation of HPC development across regions. Its global perspective contributes to Europe’s approaches remaining interoperable with international infrastructures and aligned with worldwide best practices, which is critical for globally collaborative sciences such as HEP and RA.

ETP4HPC’s Transcontinuum Initiative (TCI) is a European effort to articulate and advance the concept of a “digital continuum,” bringing together HPC, AI, big data, IoT, cybersecurity, and mathematical modelling. TCI works to define specifications and recommendations for distributed systems that must integrate diverse computational and data-intensive technologies. Its outputs aim to inform EU research agendas and Horizon Europe missions, including climate adaptation, health, and digital twins. TCI is highly relevant for SPECTRUM, as it provides a cross-domain framework for integrating complex workflows that combine simulation, AI, and real-time data processing.

EUCloudEdgeIoT and the OpenContinuum project focus on building bridges across the cloud–edge–IoT ecosystem. OpenContinuum has produced a reference architecture structured around building blocks for security, trust, orchestration, data management, networking, monitoring, and AI/ML. A key contribution is its harmonised taxonomy, which aligns definitions across the cloud, edge, and IoT domains, enabling interoperability and reducing fragmentation. Its emphasis on embedding AI into all layers of the continuum, both for operational decision-making and for scientific analysis, offers a forward-looking model for how European research infrastructures could evolve.

IPCEI-CIS (Important Projects of Common European Interest – Cloud Infrastructure and Services) represents a large-scale industrial and governmental investment in Europe’s cloud and digital services sector. The initiative aims to ensure European technological sovereignty by developing interoperable, federated cloud and edge infrastructures. Its reference architecture includes federated resource management, automated orchestration, and comprehensive security frameworks, designed for multi-provider and multi-tenant environments.

The EuroHPC Federation Platform (EFP), launched in 2025, has the goal of making access to EuroHPC resources more seamless. At present, users must manage separate accounts, allocation processes, and software environments for each system. EFP seeks to unify this through federated identity and single sign-on, consolidated allocation monitoring, and integrated workflow management across sites. Planned features include interactive SSH and web-based access (e.g. Jupyter, remote desktop), a federated software catalogue, and cross-system data transfer services. By Q1 2026, the platform aims to be in production, providing a more user-friendly interface to EuroHPC supercomputers, AI factories, and quantum systems. For researchers in HEP and RA, this is expected to simplify access to leadership-class resources while supporting heterogeneous and distributed workflows. The EFP is directly relevant to SPECTRUM’s vision of a compute–data continuum, as it offers a practical foundation for federated access and resource interoperability, complementing the blueprint’s emphasis on cross-facility workflows and harmonised user experience.